

**THE EFFECT OF LOGISTICS MANAGEMENT PRACTICE ON
ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE:**

(In Case of Kombolcha Textile Share Company).

**A Thesis Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement for the Award
of the Degree of Master of Arts in Logistics and Supply Chain Management.**

By:

Amanuel Mengistu Hailu

ID No: AKU/0906896

Advisor: Mebrahtu Teka (PhD)

**AKSUM UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS
DEPARTMENT OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN
MANAGEMENT**

June, 2018

Aksum, Tigray, Ethiopia

**APPROVAL FORM
AKSUM UNIVERSITY**

COLLEGE OF BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS

DEPARTMENT OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT

As members of the Examining Board of the final MA open defense, we certify that we have read and evaluated the Thesis prepared by **Amanuel Mengistu** entitled: ‘**The Effect of Logistics Management Practice on Organizational Performance in Case of Kombolcha Textile Share Company**’; and recommend that it be accepted as fulfilling the thesis requirement for the award of the Degree of Master of Arts in Logistics and Supply Chain Management.

<u>Dambush Negasi</u>	_____	_____
Chairman	Signature	Date
<u>Simon Zekarias (PhD)</u>	_____	_____
Internal Examiner	Signature	Date
<u>Abadi Afera (Asst.prof)</u>	_____	_____
External Examiner	Signature	Date

I hereby certify that I have read the revised version of this thesis prepared under my direction and recommend that it be accepted as fulfilling the thesis requirement.

<u>Mebrahtu Teka (PhD)</u>	_____	_____
Thesis advisor	Signature	Date
<u>Dambush Negasi</u>	_____	_____
Department chairperson	Signature	Date

DECLARATION

I, AMANUEL MENGISTU declare that the work embodied in this MasterThesis is my own work carried out by me under the supervision of Dr. **Mebrahtu Teka** from October, 2017 to June, 2018 at the Department of Logistics and Supply Chain Management, Aksum University, Aksum. The matter embodied in this master's thesis has not been submitted for the award of any other degree/diploma.

I declare that I have faithfully acknowledged, given credit to and referred to the research workers wherever their works have been cited in the text and the body of the thesis. I further certify that I have not willfully lifted up someone's work, paragraph, text, data, results, etc. reported in the journals, books, magazines, reports, dissertations, theses, etc., or available at web-sites and included them in this thesis. Thesis and cited as my own work. I also declare that I have adhered to all principles of academic honesty and integrity and have not misrepresented or fabricated or falsified any idea/data/fact/source in my submission. I understand that any violation of the above will be cause for disciplinary action by the University.

Name: **Amanuel Mengistu Hailu**

Place: Aksum University, Aksum

Signature:-----

Date: June, 2018

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I thank the almighty God for the strength, and courage throughout my study up to this stage. It is my belief that nothing could have been possible without God's blessing.

In a special way, I would like to thank my advisor, Dr. Mebrahtu Teka, for his technical advice, critical and constructive inputs and his endless commitment to support my study. It was your consistent guidance that gives me courage to make further effort to make complete this study.

I would like to thank Ms Hana Alebachew HR expert of KTSC, for a kind reception at the company and her consistent help in providing required information. I am grateful to Mr Usman, who was the main actor in distributing and returning the questionnaire. Thank you Hana and Usman I couldn't do that all without you, you were a good friend.

My special thank would go to Ato Seid Ahmed head of HR department of KTSC, under his permission the research was conducted in the company. Thank you Ato Seid, I will not forget your experience share and advice like a father and teacher.

I am also thankful for those interviewed individuals (Kedir from marketing, Usman from procurement and property control); this study was incomplete without your valuable information.

Sincere gratitude should go to my friends Andualem, Debela, Haile and amero, I am so happy you have been with me in all the time when I need your help. There were a lot of things that I couldn't do without you. Thank you my friends.

Lastly, I thank my families, mother-father and brothers-sisters: as they have always been supportive morally and materially. I could never disregard their contribution for my life journey. I would not have made it this far without them.

List of Acronyms

BTRE	Bureau of Transport and Regional Economics of Australia
CS	Customer service
CSCMP	Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals
CSP	Customer service policy
EDI	Electronic Data Interchange
EOQ	Economic Order Quantity
ERP	Enterprise Resource planning
FIFO	first in first out
GPS	Geographic positioning system
ICT	Information communication technology
IM	Inventory management
JIT	Just in time
KTSC	Kombolcha textile Share Company
LIS	Logistics information systems
LP	Logistics performance
MRP	Material requirement planning
OE	Orders entry
OP	Organizational performance
RFID	Radio-Frequency Identification
SMEs	Small and medium scale enterprises
SM	Supply management
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
SSP	Supplier Service Policy
TM	Transportation management
VIF	Variance inflation factor
WM	Warehouse management
3PL	Third-party logistics

Table of Contents

Contents	Page No.
APPROVAL FORM	i
DECLARATION	ii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iii
List of Acronyms	iv
Table of Contents	v
List of Tables	ix
List of Figures	ix
Abstract	x
CHAPTER ONE	1
1.1 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.2 Background of the Study.....	1
1.3 Statement of the Problem	4
1.4 Basic Research Questions	6
1.5 Research Objective.....	6
1.5.1 General Objective	6
1.5.2 Specific Objectives	6
1.6 Significance of the Study	7
1.7 Scope of the Study.....	7
1.8 Organization of the Paper.....	8
CHAPTER TWO	9
REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE	9
2.1 Introduction	9
2.2 Evolution and Definitions of Logistics Management	9
2.3 Logistics Activities/Practices	11
2.3.1 Customer Service.....	11
2.3.1 Inventory Management.....	13
2.3.3 Supply Management / Procurement	14
2.3.4 Transportation Management.....	15

2.3.5 Warehousing Management	17
2.3.6 Logistics Information System.....	19
2.4 Logistics Performance.....	21
2.4.1 Logistics Cost	22
2.4.2 Logistics Service Quality.....	23
2.4.3 Time to Deliver.....	24
2.4.4 Logistics Flexibility	26
2.5 Organizational Performance.....	27
2.6 Empirical Review of Studies.....	28
2.7 Logistics Practice in Ethiopian Case.....	31
2.8 Conceptual Framework	32
CHAPTER THREE	34
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY.....	34
3.1 INTRODUCTION.....	34
3.2 Description of the Study Area.....	34
3.3 Research Design	34
3.4 Research Approach	35
3.5 Sampling and Sampling Techniques	36
3.5.1 Target Population	36
3.5.2 Sampling Techniques	36
3.5.3 Sample Size	37
3.6 Data Type and Source of Data	38
3.7 Data Gathering Technique and Instruments.....	39
3.8 Data Analysis	39
3.9 Validity and Reliability	40
3.9.1 Reliability	40
3.9.2 Validity	42
3.10 Ethical issues.....	42
CHAPTER FOUR.....	43
DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION	43
4.1 Introduction	43

4.2 Response Rate	43
4.3 Respondent Profile	44
4.4 Descriptive Statistics	46
4.4.1 Customer Service.....	46
4.4.2 Inventory Planning and Management.....	49
4.4.3 Supply Management	52
4.4.4 Transportation Management.....	55
4.4.5 Warehouse Management	58
Table 4.7- Warehouse Management	58
4.4.6 Logistics Information System.....	61
4.4.7 Logistics Performance measures	65
4.4.8 Organizational Performance	70
4.5 Inferential Statistics.....	72
4.5.1 Correlation Analysis	72
4.5.1.1 Correlation between logistics practice dimensions and logistics performance	72
4.5.1.2 Correlation between combined logistics dimensions and logistics performance ..	74
4.5.1.3 Correlation between Logistics practice dimensions and organizational performance	75
4.5.1.4 Correlation between combined logistics practice dimensions and organizational performance	77
4.5.1.5 Correlation between Logistics performance measures and organizational performance	77
4.5.1.6 Correlation between collective logistics performance measures and organizational performance	79
4.5.2 Regression Analysis	80
4.5.2.1 Multicollinearity Test.....	80
4.5.2.2 Normality Test	81
4.5.2.3 Heteroscedasticity Test	81
4.5.2.4 Regression of logistics performance on logistics practice dimensions.....	82
4.5.2.5 Regression of organizational performance on logistics practice dimensions	84
4.5.2.6 Regression of Organizational Performance on Logistics Performance Measures.	86
CHAPTER FIVE	89

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	89
5.1 INTRODUCTION.....	89
5.2 SUMMARY	89
5.3 CONCLUSION	93
5.4 RECOMMENDATIONS	95
5.5 LIMITATION AND FURTHER RESEARCH DIRECTIONS.....	97
REFERENCE.....	98
APPENDIX I- Questionnaire.....	106
APPENDIX II- Interview Questions	113
Appendix III-Multicollinearity Test	114
Appendix IV-Normality Test.....	115
Appendix V- Heteroscedasticity Test.....	116

List of Tables

Table: 3.1 numbers of classes with the corresponding population	37
Table: 3.2 Number of respondents which will be taken from each class	38
Table 3.3-Reliability test results	41
Table 4.1-Response Rate	43
Table 4.2-Profile of Respondents	44
Table 4.3- Customer Service.....	47
Table 4.4- Inventory Management.....	50
Table 4.5- Supply Management.....	53
Table 4.6- Transportation Management.....	56
Table 4.7- Warehouse Management	58
Table 4.8- Logistics Information System.....	61
Table 4.9- Perception of respondents on Logistics Performance Measures	65
Table 4.10- Perception of respondents on Organizational Performance	70
Table 4.11-correlation between logistics practice dimensions and logistics performance	72
Table 4.12-correlation between combined logistics dimensions and logistics performance.....	74
Table 4.13-correlation between logistics practice dimensions and organizational performance .	75
Table 4.14-correlation between combined logistics dimensions and organizational performance	77
Table 4.15-correlation between logistics performance measures and organizational performance	77
Table 4.16-Correlation between collective logistics performance measures and organizational performance.	79
Table 4.17- Regression of logistics performance on logistics practice dimensions	82
Table 4.19-Regression of organizational performance on logistics performance measures	86
Table 4.18-Regression of organizational performance on logistics practice dimensions.....	84

List of Figures

Figure 2.1: The research framework.....	33
---	----

Abstract

Logistics is in charge of managing supply through serving customers from which a firm obtains cash. The purpose of this study was to assess the logistics practices and the impact that logistics has on organizational performance in the case of kombolcha textile Share Company. This research is cross sectional and associational in design. So as to attain the objectives of the study, stratified sampling method have been employed in order to get a precise sample size. Both quantitative and qualitative data were used. Questionnaire and semi-structured interview were employed as a research instruments to collect primary data. The quantitative data was collected from 128 employees of kombolcha textile Share Company who are directly or indirectly involved in logistics activities and the interview was conducted with two department heads from marketing and procurement. The quantitative data were analyzed using statistical package for social science version 20. Descriptive statistics, percentage, mean and standard deviation were computed to describe each of the variables. Inferential statistics, correlation, particularly Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple linear regression analysis were made to test the relationship and influence among independent and dependent variables. The qualitative data were narrated in parallel with quantitative results. The quantitative result revealed that logistics dimensions, customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management, warehouse management and logistics information system have highly practiced in the company but the qualitative data does not support this and proved that there is no well integrated logistics functioning in the company. The identifying logistics practice dimensions have positive association with logistics as well as organizational performance. Logistics performance measures; cost, quality, time to deliver and flexibility has also positive association with organizational performance. Customer service and logistics information system have found to be significant influence on logistics performance. But only logistics information system has significant influence on organizational performance. The other logistics practice dimensions found to be insignificant in this research data set. Only logistics flexibility has significant impact on organizational performance. The other logistics performance measures cost, quality and time to deliver have also found to be insignificant in this study data set. Therefore; KTSC should take improvement actions in its way of managing logistics process to benefit from best logistics system.

Key words: *logistics practice, logistics performance, organizational performance, KTSC.*

CHAPTER ONE

1.1 INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the general background of the study. It presents brief background information on the role of logistics in order to see the significance of the problem. Furthermore, this chapter contains statement of the problem, research questions, the main and specific objectives of the study, significance of the study and organization of the paper as presented in the following sections.

1.2 Background of the Study

All around the globe, 24 hours of every day, 7 days a week, during 52 weeks a year, logistics is concerned with getting products and services where they are needed at the precise time desired. It is difficult to visualize accomplishing any marketing, manufacturing, or international commerce without logistics. It is through the logistical process that materials flow into the manufacturing capacity of an industrial nation and products are distributed to consumers (Bowersox, Closs and Cooper, 2002). The ability to transport goods quickly, safely, economically and reliably (logistics) is seen as vital to success of businesses, and to a nation's prosperity and capacity to compete in globalized economy (Fekadu, 2013).

The Council of Supply Chain Management Professionals (CSCMP) defines logistics management as the process of planning, implementing, and controlling procedures for the efficient and effective transportation and storage of goods including services, and related information from the point of origin to the point of consumption for the purpose of conforming to customer requirements. This definition includes inbound, outbound, internal, and external movements (Robinson, 2013). Business logistics consists of Inventory management, purchasing, transportation and warehousing which can be defined as having the right item in the right quantity at right time at the right place for the right price. Logistics activities are vital for both manufacturing and service organizations to be competitive in today's market conditions (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008). Activities such as procurement, inventory management, warehousing, materials management, distribution and customer service, which are included in logistics should be well-thought out in advance, well-coordinated and above all should be facilitating the achievement of the overall goals of a company (Kotsifaki et al., 2007). Superior logistics practices represent an important option not only because they can lead to more efficient operations but because they can effectively increase customer loyalty (Christopher, 2011).

Ellinger et al., (2000) demonstrated that logistics is a strategic vector in companies' organization and influences their performance, namely in terms of service quality and overall profitability. Some of the key logistics practices that impact performance is related to estimation of customer needs, efficient and effective delivery, integration and collaboration throughout the supply chain, sharing of information as well as informal methods and use of specialists for performing specific jobs across the supply chain, all of these practices impact logistics performance significantly (Fekadu, 2013). As mentioned by Mentzer et al., (2001) besides with its internal importance, logistics also has an impact on effectiveness and profitability. Logistics lies at the core of both operational and marketing processes. It is actually logistics that provides companies with the ability to effectively and efficiently meet their customers' requirements. Without appropriate configuration and implementation of the whole logistics function, companies are risking being rigid, disorientated and ultimately being driven out of the market (Kotsifaki et al., 2007). Logistics is a channel of the supply chain which adds the value of time and place utility. In Textile Industry where so many stages are need to pass from Raw materials to finished goods and then to reach at customers end within stipulated time frame, the logistics management plays a vital role in satisfying customers need and brings delighters in business circle. Most textile manufacturers handle all logistics functions including trucking and warehousing through their own logistics and transportation departments (Kapleand and Jadha, 2017).

Ethiopia's textile and clothing sector has experienced a boom in export-led growth in recent years, and the sector is characterized by strong value addition throughout the entire value chain from cotton to clothing, with high local processing of cotton lint into textile and apparel products. The textile industry is considered to be one of the first steps into industrialization and give opportunities for employment and increase the possibilities for global trading (International trade center [ITC], 2016). Accordingly, the Ethiopian textile sector is facing a fierce competition for raw material and markets due to the coming of foreign firms to the sector especially from china, India, Indonesia, Turkish and due to the establishment of industrial parks. This is a big deal for the country's economic development and employment opportunities. However; this warns the existing textile firms to look seriously at their functional areas to struggle with the competition. One way that firms can win such competition is through logistics excellence (ITC, 2016). Kombolcha textile Share Company is one of the textile firms in Ethiopia competing for cotton and market for its final products. Clearly working well at logistics activities can enable

firms to minimize costs and enhance customer service quality and would have significant effect on organizations performance. Measuring logistics performance reduce operating costs (helps identify whether and where to make operational changes to control expenses and identifies areas for improved asset management); drive revenue growth (attract and retain valuable customers, the price/value of products offered can be enhanced through cost reductions and service improvements in logistics activities); enhance shareholder value (The returns on shareholder investments and the market value of the firm are impacted by the performance of firms logistics) (Campagna, 2009).The close relationship between logistics management and customer service, and its effect on a firm's competitiveness dictate that firms needs to handle their logistics function prudently so as to achieve its full potential as a source of competitive advantage (Kotsifaki et al., 2007).

Chow et al, (1994) explained that logistics performance may be considered as a subset of the larger portion of firm or organizational performance. Logistics performance can be measured in a variety of ways for example; Christopher (2011) considers time, cost and quality as three key performance measures which should form part of any logistics Performance measurement system. This is because these measures contribute more than proportionally to the success or failure of a firm. Based on the available literature on logistics performance this research considers logistics Cost, logistics service Quality, Time to deliver, and logistics flexibility as a measure of logistics performance. According to Richard et al., (2009) firm performance encompasses three specific areas of firm outcomes: financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment); market performance (sales, market share); and, customer satisfaction/value added. Market share, the growth in market share, the growth in sales, return on investment, growth in return on investment, profit margin on sales and overall competitive position have proposed for this study as firm performance indicators which has both natures of financial and market oriented objectives. Thus, the literature shows that logistics practices from a variety of different perspectives with a common goal of ultimately providing customers place and time utility and improving organizational performance. In conducting this research, logistics activities, including customer service, inventory management, supply/procurement, transportation, warehouse management and logistics information system are selected for measuring logistics practice. Therefore, this research is intended to test the framework

considered the relationships among logistics practices, logistics performance measures and organizational performance of the case company (kombolcha textile Share Company).

1.3 Statement of the Problem

In an era of shrinking product life cycles, proliferation of product lines, shifting distribution chains and rapidly changing technological advancement, use of logistics had become an essential ingredient for organizations in gaining competitive advantage (Njambi and Katuse, 2013). This is due to the fact that managing logistics activities balances two basic objectives: Quality of Service and Low Cost of doing business as every other firms objective lies on quality of service and minimum production cost (Bowersox et al., 2002). Logistics management has the potential to assist the organization in the achievement of both a cost advantage and a value advantage. Effective logistics management can provide a major source of competitive advantage to a company (Christopher, 2011).

The management of logistics process improves competitiveness and performance through timely availability of conforming product in the marketplace at low cost or say differently logistics is critical in meeting end-customer demand through supplying what is needed in the form it is needed, when it is needed, at a competitive cost (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008). This would enable firms so as to secure competitive advantage and improving organizational performance. Bagshaw (2017) investigated logistics management and firm performance and confirmed that logistics activities have influence on firm performance on the rate of production output, market share and profitability. Ristovska, kozuharov and Petkovski (2017) Explore impact of company's logistics on efficiency and effectiveness performance and revealed that reduction of the cost of each logistics activity influences the total amount of costs and enhances company's performance and optimally manage all logistics activities results in increased business efficiency, customer satisfaction and competitiveness. An analysis by Ilic and Tesic (2016) pointed that logistics and supply chain management practices have associated benefits such as lower cost, higher quality, better customer service, flexibility and improved competitive advantage. Research findings on the area of logistics practice in Ethiopia as well as particular to business firms revealed that logistics is not fully understood yet and still it is poor in practice. The logistics performance of Ethiopia is characterized by lack of coordination in the chain, lack of coordination in areas of inventory planning and warehouse management, less attention on customer satisfaction, inadequate vehicles in delivery of goods to customers and also lack of coordination with

transporters (Fekadu, 2013). A study on logistics practice in Ethiopian manufacturing by (Melkamu, 2016; Afomeya, 2016; Tura and Efa 2017) indicate that logistic component has not been given the required attention and inefficient transportation, less developed warehouse facility, and longer lead times, interrupted production and information flow are apparent. The competitiveness of Ethiopian textile and garment industry is not capable of competing in the international markets due to logistics and value chain shortcomings as lack of experience in dealing with domestic as well as international suppliers and customers, low productivity and limited quality awareness, long production and delivery lead time, Poor logistics and supply chain information channel, transportation and warehouse facility bottlenecks (Daniel and Amare, n.d.).

Since it is established in 1984 Kombolcha textile Share Company is engaged in the production of 100% cotton products. To produce superior quality cotton products the company is highly dependent on local suppliers of state and private cotton farms such as (Soudi star AD PLC; Sabina industrial plc; Ras dashion (Gonder); Motoma union; OMO valley and Tegegne Alemu Selam union). Even more those cotton suppliers are diversely located in different parts of the country. Failure to do well with those suppliers can stop the company's production since lint cotton is its major input for production. Excellent logistics on its supply base can help the company to achieve significant cost savings and to feed its production the required quality cotton. On the other hand maintaining strong relationship with suppliers and excel at supply logistics activities would keep the company uninterrupted in production and will enhance its logistics performance. It also observed that running out of stock at the factory sales center for most of its products is a common phenomenon. The company need to understand the impact that stock out has on its sales and profit margins as well for its customer's satisfaction. Besides this major portion of the company's products are exported and sold to foreign markets like (America, Italian, China, German, Swaziland, srael) and making available products in those market is another area of the company's logistics which needs serious attention since simple failure in warehousing and transportation logistics in delivery can have significant impact on the performance of the company. There are also local targets for the company's product in different parts of Ethiopia particularly regional urban centers addis ababa, mekele, bahirdar, dessie and kombolcha. Hence the logistics of providing quality product at short lead time can enhance the company's revenue, customer service and greatly improves its market share. In other words, the

logistics role should optimize the flow of goods in order to maintain quality, on time delivery and satisfaction. All this depicts that the company's existing logistics practice needs to be researched to understand the impacts that logistics has on the company's performance. Besides the mentioned gaps this research is different from other studies by considering logistics practices dimensions described by (customer service, inventory management, Supply management/procurement, transportation, warehouse management and logistics information system) and the relationship that exists between logistics practice, logistics performance and organizational performances on kombolcha textile Share Company. Therefore, this research is designed to contribute to the existing literature in logistics by testing the relationship between logistics practice measurements and logistics performance measures and organizational performance in the case company.

1.4 Basic Research Questions

In addition to the above mentioned gap, the following research questions are formulated to be answered in the course of the research:

1. What is the current logistics practice of kombolcha textile Share Company?
2. What is the relationship between logistics practice and logistics performance?
3. What is the relationship between logistics practice and organizational performance?
4. What is the relationships between logistics performance measures and organizational performance?

1.5 Research Objective

1.5.1 General Objective

The overall purpose of this study is to describe logistics practices and analyze the relationship among logistics practice, logistics performance measures and firm performance with the focus on the case company.

1.5.2 Specific Objectives

More specifically this research aims at addressing the following specific objectives.

1. To describe the existing logistics practice of kombolcha textile share company.
2. To examine the relationship between logistics practice and logistics performance.
3. To investigate the relationship between logistics practice and organizational performance.

4. To investigate the relationship between logistics performance measures and organizational performance.

1.6 Significance of the Study

Examining logistics practices and its correlation with logistics performance and organizational performance can provide the following benefits generally for the academicians, researchers, and businesses who want excel in logistics, and specifically, for the case company. Additionally the study is conducted in an environment where logistics practice has yet to mature. In Ethiopia still there are colleges and public universities which are not provide logistics as a discipline and as well the business arena which is on the way of development. Thus, the research will contribute for the development of the discipline.

Particularly this study will have the following benefits;

- Help to better understand the processes of logistics practices in related with the company under consideration.
- Use as a guideline to facilitate a more open and transparent communication and cooperation among the functional areas of the company.
- Contribute to narrow the gap in the literature on the generalization of the causal relationship between logistics practices and performance.
- Help as a reference for future researchers who are willing to conduct study on the area of logistics.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The geographic scope of this study is limited to the case company (kombatolcha textile share company) located in south wollo, kombatolcha. The subject matter scope of this study is limited to logistics practice variables including customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation, warehouse management and logistics information system. In terms of firm performance the study is delimited to logistics performance (which is measured by Cost, quality, Time and flexibility) and organizational performance (market share, the growth in market share, return on investment, growth in return on investment, the growth in sales, profit margin on sales and overall competitive position). Logistics is also classified as emergency (humanitarian) logistics and business logistics and this research concentrates on the business aspects of logistics with the case company. This research is conducted the time elapsed between October 2017 and may end 2018.

1.8 Organization of the Paper

The entire thesis of this study is organized as: - Chapter one: introduction part of the study while chapter two: reviews the related literature on logistics practice and organizational performance, chapter three: research methodology then chapter four: data presentation and analysis and chapter five: summary, concluding remarks and recommendation have been given.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

The literature review of this study is to address evolution and influence of logistics, empirical review and logistics practice in Ethiopian case related to the topic of the study. It includes definition and concept such as logistics management, logistics performance and organizational performance by focusing on previous research conducted in this area and present reviewed literature relevant to this study.

2.2 Evolution and Definitions of Logistics Management

Logistics was initially a military activity concerned with getting soldiers and munitions to the battle front in time for flight; The term, was developed in the context of military activities in the late 18th and early 19th centuries and it launched from the military logistics of World War II. The possible origin of the term is the Greek *logistikos*, meaning ‘skilled in calculating’. Military definitions normally incorporate the supply, movement and quartering of troops in a set but it is now seen as an integral part of the modern production process (Bureau of Transport and Regional Economics of Australia [BTRE], 2001). Before the 1950s Physical distribution begins to emerge as an area of study and practice, which is the coordination of more than one activity associated with physically supplying product to the marketplace (Ballou, 2007). Even if physical distribution is usually connected with outbound product movements from a firm, the definition indicates a broader concept that includes both inbound and outbound movements of materials and products (Ballou, 2007). Physical distribution was able to coordinate the management of transport, warehousing, inventory management, materials handling, and order processing. the activities currently associated with logistics was a fragmented and often uncoordinated set of activities spread throughout various organizational functions such as marketing, finance, and production (Brewer, 2001). This fragmentation led to conflicts among those responsible for logistics activities with the result that, from the firm’s perspective, costs and customer service were sub-optimized (Ballou, 2007).

In the 1960s, material handling, warehousing, and traffic were grouped collectively to become known as physical distribution; procurement, marketing, and customer service were grouped together to become known as business logistics. Even today in many educational institutions, logistics is still alienated along these lines; where logistics is taught in the business school, it is

taught as business logistics and in the engineering schools as physical distribution (Frazelle, 2002). For long periods logistics management and physical distribution were treated as they are same and used interchangeably. However, now the two functions are very different from each other. Logistics management includes many activities from supplying the materials to customer satisfaction. On the other hand, physical distribution is one function of logistics and mainly concerned in only distributing final products to the customers (Ozalp, Suvaci, and Tonus, 2010). Logistics is now being viewed as a subset of supply chain management; there are numerous confusion and arguments regarding the terms logistics and supply chain management. Frazelle distinguished the two by explaining that supply chain is the network of facilities (warehouses, factories, terminals, ports, stores, and homes), vehicles (trucks, trains, planes, and ocean vessels), and logistics information systems (LIS) connected by an enterprise's supplier's suppliers and its customer's customers. Logistics is what happens in the supply chain. Logistics activities (customer response, inventory management, supply, transportation, and warehousing) connect and activate the objects in the supply chain through logistics information system. Supply chain is a field which is broader focuses where as logistics is the activity or operations which is played or activated in the supply chain field (Frazelle, 2002). Supply chain management is broader in scope than logistics. Researchers in the area of logistics and supply chain management dispute that this broad area and objective of supply chain management will result in loss of its focus and identity.

The logistics management involves planning, implementing and controlling efficient, effective flow and storage of goods and services from the beginning point of external origin to the company and from the company to the point of consumption for the purpose of conforming to customer requirements. Logistics is generally viewed as within one company, although it manages flow between company and its suppliers and customers (Lummus et al., 2001). Logistics advantages came from in the form of such competitive factors as better product availability in the marketplace and low product obsolescence or speed delivery and of quality, better response time and cost efficiency (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008). Logistics is the task of managing material flow of the physical goods from suppliers through the distribution centers to stores; information flow of demand data from the end-customer back to purchasing and to suppliers, and supply data from suppliers to the retailer, so that material flow can be accurately planned and controlled (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008).

Logistics is the process of strategically managing the procurement, movement and storage of materials, parts and finished inventory (and the related information flows) through the organization and its marketing channels in such a way that current and future profitability are maximized through the cost-effective fulfillment of orders (Christopher, 2011). This notion of logistics depicts that logistics has now become an integral part of business in connection with the flow of materials, funds, information and this definition depicts that logistics extends from sourcing raw material/supply management, materials management to delivering final products to customers and this is the operational definition for this research.

2.3 Logistics Activities/Practices

In spite of its obvious importance, logistics has not always received its fair share of attention. Historically, organizations put their entire endeavor into making products and gave little consideration to the associated movement of materials. Managers accepted that transport and storage were needed, but they were viewed as technical issues that were not worth much attention; they were simply the inevitable costs of doing business (Waters, 2003). Logistics represents a collection of activities that ensures the availability of the right products in the right quantity to the right customers at the right time. Logistics activities serve as a link between production and consumption and provide a bridge between production and market locations or suppliers separated by a distance and time. The main purpose of logistics is to coordinate a bunch of related activities which work together to create a supply chain and provide time and location benefits for customers (Ozalp et al., 2010). A common way to structure a company, from a logistics perspective, is in three main activities: procurement, operations and distribution (Christopher, 2011). However, the typical elements of logistic activities, such as customer services, sales forecasting, distribution communications, stock control, materials handling and ordering, amongst others, may give companies competitive advantages, especially when based on the exchange of reliable information between the links in the chain (Bowersox et al., 2002).

2.3.1 Customer Service

According to Frazelle the logistics of customer response includes the practices of developing and maintaining a customer service policy (CSP), monitoring customer satisfaction, orders entry (OE), order processing (OP), and invoicing and collections. Customer demand is the foundation for all the rest of logistics activities. Satisfying customer orders creates the need for all logistics resources and activities. The objective of each of the other logistics processes should be to satisfy

the customer response requirements at the lowest possible cost (Frazelle, 2002). The role of customer service in logistics supply chain systems will continue to change. Therefore, the need to improve logistics customer service to consumers is greater than ever before. Increasing customer service raises customer satisfaction and increased customer satisfaction improves corporate performance (Bowersox et al., 2002). Customer service is a necessary requirement in logistics activities and is affected by various environmental factors shaping today's marketplace. Logistics customer service represents the best opportunity for a firm to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage (Waters, 2010). It is often suggested that the role of logistics is to provide "time and place utility" in the transfer of goods and services between buyer and seller. In other words, there is no value in the product or the service until it is in the hands of the customer. It follows that making the product or service "available" is what the logistics function of the business is all about (Christopher, 2011).

Customer service is one of the most critical factors in attracting new and retaining old customers, and improving the competitive position of the company on the market as well. The main field of activity of the customer service is in charge of the logistics activities of a company. The most important influence on the policy of the customer service has major logistics functions: transport, inventory keeping, warehousing and the logistics information system (Melovic et al., 2015). While in some ways it's an insight into the obvious, it is important to establish initially that logistics contributes to an organization's success by accommodating customers' delivery and availability expectations and requirements (Bowersox, 2002). Ultimately the success or failure of any business will be determined by the level of customer value that it delivers in its chosen markets. Customer value can be defined quite simply as the difference between the perceived benefits that flow from a purchase or a relationship and the total costs incurred (Christopher, 2011). Customer service represents a measure of the efficiency of the logistics system in creating time and space value for the product, including after-sales activities of the company. In the highly competitive market of final products, the level of customer service can help firms get new and/or retain old customers (Melovic et al., 2015). Frazelle, (2002) argues that in today's just-in-time world the ability to respond to customers' requirements in ever-shorter time-frames has become critical. Most authors and practitioners agree that building and enhancing long-term relationships with customers generates positive returns to firms (Reichheld, 1996). To do this the whole purpose of supply chain management and logistics is to provide customers with the level

and quality of service that they require and to do so at less cost to the total supply chain (Christopher, 2011). The process of the customer service involves all those activities that facilitate customers to get to the required-new product, or which allows consumers to purchase. Companies can rarely achieve the satisfaction process of their customers. Therefore, the customer service is put in the value chain activities of the delivery. The more efficient the customer service is, the more opportunities the company will have to achieve competitive advantage in the market, with increased sales, market share and profit (Melovic et al., 2015).

2.3.1 Inventory Management

Inventory management includes activities of forecasting, order quantity engineering, service level optimization, replenishment planning, and inventory deployment (Frazelle, 2002). Well managed inventory will lead to organization to have optimal inventory level and to eliminate the costs associated with holding too much and too little inventory. Inventory levels have been seen as one of the most interesting areas for improvement in organization materials management (Kumar, Ordamar, and Zhang, 2008). Inventory plays a significant role in the growth and survival of an organization in the sense that ineffective and inefficient management of inventory will mean that the organization loses customers and sales will decline. Prudent management of inventory reduces depreciation, pilferage, and wastages while ensuring availability of the materials as at when required (Ogbad, 2009). Inventory management is critical to an organization's success in today's competitive and dynamic market. This entails a reduction in the cost of holding stocks by maintaining just enough inventories, in the right place and the right time and cost to make the right amount of needed products. Performance measures such that cost, flexibility, time and quality appear to be highly influenced by Inventory control. According to Burman (1995) this activity influences costs because inventory control contributes not only to keep a low level of products but also to remove all sources of waste, contributing to a decrease on costs. Furthermore, a good inventory control allows firms to keep an adequate level of inventory in order to increase its responsiveness to the market; exceed the gap of time between suppliers and consumers; and support Just-in-time programs between suppliers, sellers, and customers (Stock and Lambert, 2001). Beyond the impact of this activity on costs, flexibility and time, the quality of logistics service seems also to be influenced by inventory control and, more exactly, by the level of inventory (Closs and Thompson, 1999). Inventory turnover has a favorable result on firm's performance which was determined by sales return. In addition,

inventory reduction has also a favorable impact on organization performance (Demeter, 2003). Therefore, inventory management plays a crucial role in balancing the benefits and disadvantages associated with holding inventory. When organizations fail to manage their inventory effectively they are bound to experience, stock out, the decline in productivity and profitability, customer dissatisfaction (Bowersox et al., 2002).

High levels of inventory held in stock affect adversely the procurement performance out of the capital being held which affects cash flow leading to reduced efficiency, effectiveness and distorted functionality (Koin, Cheruiyot, and Mwangangi, 2014). Theoretically, a firm could stock every item sold in every facility dedicated to servicing each customer, but very few business operations could afford such an expensive inventory deployment strategy because the risk and total cost is prohibitive (Bowersox et al., 2002). Excessive inventories would compensate for deficiencies in basic design of a logistics system but ultimately resulted in higher-than-necessary total logistics cost. Understanding the interrelationship between order processing, inventory, transportation, and facility network decisions is fundamental to integrated logistics which provided great opportunity for firm performance (Kumar et al., 2008).

2.3.3 Supply Management / Procurement

Frazelle demonstrated that the logistics of supply include developing and maintaining a Supplier Service Policy (SSP), sourcing, supplier integration, purchase order processing and buying and payment. He also mentioned that the world-class sourcing practices include Make-buy analysis, total acquisition cost analysis, global sourcing, and electronic bid-based sourcing. In addition to this, World-class practices in buying and payment include central buying-local delivery, buying partnerships, and electronic funds transfer (Frazelle 2002). Supply management in logistics is designed to leverage the strategic and operational capabilities of individual participating organizations to help them achieve significant ongoing benefits (Suhong et al., 2004). Supply management is focused on the acquisition process recognizing the supply chain and organizational contexts. Special emphasis is on decision making that aligns the supplier network and the acquisition process with organizational goals and strategies and ensures short- and long-term value for funds spent. The overall objective of supply management is to minimize the total acquisition cost while meeting the availability, response time and quality requirement stipulated in the customer service policy (Meng, 2006). New purchasing and supply management practices in the commercial sector have been reported to substantially improve performance and reduce

the costs of purchased goods and services. For a firm to deliver maximum value to its customers, it must receive maximum value from all its suppliers in the supply chain (Moore et al., 2002).

It is also demonstrated that by treating suppliers as allies and sharing strategic information with them, firms can achieve better lead times and quality, increase operating flexibility, and establish long-term cost reductions, all of which could help these firms enhance value for the ultimate customer (Ondoro, Ojera, and Oginda, 2013).

Moore et al. (2002) argued that delivery performance improvements from adopting supply management, which include improved supplier responsiveness and reliability, allow firms to reduce their inventory levels. Many purchasing and supply management initiatives reportedly produce both cost savings and performance improvements. The effort towards strong cooperation between buyers and suppliers also results from the global and competitive market place that focuses on cost, quality, delivery, flexibility, and technology, which subsequently create a greater need to emphasize inter-firm collaboration with various business partners (Ondoro et al., 2013). Frazelle (2002) explained that best supply management indicators are e-procurement, supplier certification and award programs, demand information sharing, supplier visibility, supplier information sharing, supplier partnership. By successfully adopting purchasing and supply management practices firms are experiencing benefits of Short- and long-term cost savings, reduction in total ownership cost or improvements in the performance (e.g., quality, responsiveness, and flexibility), delivery performance, product development of internal production lines (Moore et al., 2002). This indicates that supply management interface capability aims for increasing responsiveness when properly integrated. A higher level of supply management interface capability automatically results in integration of logistics activities through seamless connection between suppliers and the manufacturer. It creates a strong positive influence on firm performance through the development of joint resources and the exchange of valuable information (Ondoro et al., 2013).

2.3.4 Transportation Management

Transportation management is another important activity in logistics. Improved transportation management may cause to increased sales, increased marketshare and ultimately to increased profit contribution and growth. Transportation adds “place” value to a firm’s product (Ozalp et al., 2010). Transport system is the most important economic activity among the components of business logistics systems. Transport management is the planning, controlling and decision

making on operational area of logistics that geographically moved and positioned inventory (Bowersox, et al., 2002). Today, organizations are concerned about transportation management because transportation represents a major expense item. Transportation occupies one-third of the amount in the logistics costs and hence transportation systems influence the performance of logistics system hugely (Tseng and Yue, 2005). Transportation is the key element in a logistics chain, which joints the separated activities. A logistical system should be designed to minimize the transport cost in relation to the total system cost. Through transport goods could be sent to the right place at right time in order to satisfy customers' demands. Without well designed transport systems, logistics could not bring its advantages into full play. Transportation makes goods and products movable and provides timely and regional efficacy to promote value-added under the least cost principle. Transport affects the results of logistics activities and of course, it influences production and sale (Tseng and Yue, 2005).

Transporting is required in the whole production procedures, from manufacturing to delivery to the final consumers and returns. Only a good management and coordination between each component of transport would bring the benefits of logistics to a maximum. A good transport management in logistics activities could provide better logistics efficiency, reduce operation cost, and promote service quality on firms (Bowersox et al., 2002). Transportation enhances the value of goods by providing time and place utility. That is, effective and efficient transportation moves products to points where there is a demand for the product and at a time when it is needed at desirable cost (Waters, 2010). Obviously, a product has more value at a retail store than it did in a firm's warehouse, because in the retail store it is available for sale (Iaird, 2012). At the store it could generate revenue, while in the warehouse it is simply sitting there waiting to be moved. This is where transportation added value to goods. Whether the good was moved from the manufacturer to the warehouse and then to a retail store, straight from the manufacturer to the retail store, or simply from one warehouse to the next, the product became more valuable to the company as it moved closer to the end user (Iaird, 2012). From the logistical system point of view, three factors were fundamental to transportation performance: cost, speed, and consistency (Bowersox et al., 2002). The cost of transport is the payment for shipment between two geographical locations and the expenses related to maintaining on-transit inventory. Logistical systems utilized transportation that minimized total system cost (Bowersox et al., 2002).

According to Bowersox et al.,(2002) speed of transportation was the time required to complete a specific movement. Speed and cost of transportation were related in two ways. First, transport firms capable of offering faster delivery typically charged higher rates for their services. Second, the faster the transportation service was, the shorter the time interval during which inventory were on transit and the higher the charges (Bowersox et al., 2002). Thus, a critical aspect of selecting the most desirable method of transportation to a firm is to balance speed and cost of service. By shipping in car loads or truckload quantities rather than less than carloads or less than truckload quantities, a company may experience lower per unit transportation rates (Ozalp et al., 2010). As long as the transportation cost savings exceed any expenses associated with warehousing the additional volumes of product, it will be advantageous to ship in the larger quantities. Also, shipments in large volumes may experience better service, such as faster transit times and more reliable and consistent service. These results will help to reduce other costs such as in transit inventory carrying cost and potential costs of lost sales due to product unavailability at point of sale or use (Meng, 2006). In some circumstances low-cost, slow transportation is satisfactory. In other situations, faster service will be essential to achieving operating goals. Finding and managing the desired transportation mix across the supply chain is a primary responsibility of logistics management (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008).

2.3.5 Warehousing Management

A warehouse is typically viewed as a place to hold or store inventory. However, in contemporary logistical systems, warehouse functionality can be more properly viewed as inventory mixing. While effective logistics systems should not be designed to hold inventory for extended times, there are occasions when inventory storage is justified on the basis of cost and service (Bowersox et al., 2002). Warehousing is an important part of a firm's logistics system that stores products (raw materials, parts, goods-in-process and finished goods) at and between points of origin and points of consumption. Warehousing can be provided by either warehouses or distribution centers (Murphy et al., 2008). Christopher (2011) lists the roles of warehouses as being make/break bulk consolidation centers, transshipment facilities, assembly facilities, product fulfillment centers, returned goods depots and other miscellaneous roles such as customer support. This therefore means that warehouses play a key role in supporting supply chain strategies particularly when it is facilitated with warehouse management system software's, radio frequency identification tool and advanced ICT tools. The direct labor and capital invested

in warehouse operations equipment is a significant element of total logistics cost. When performed in an inferior manner, warehouse operations can result in substantial product damage (Bowersox et al., 2002). The roles of warehouses are being seen as increasingly important as they change from holding yards to switching yards. Warehousing is one of the important auxiliaries to trade. It creates time utility by bridging the time gap between production and consumption of goods.). They may simply serve markets or hold inventory and therefore provide means for achieving appropriate customer service and cost reduction in an environment prone to long lead times and disruptions (Christopher, 2011). Sarkis and Saundaraj (2002) identify strategic considerations as a criterion, operationalized as competition, current facilities, market size and penetration as well as expansion capabilities. According to Stock and Lambert (2001) warehouse management contribute to a multitude of the company's missions, like; Achieving transportation economies (e.g. combine shipment, full-container load), achieving production economies (e.g. make-to-stock production policy), taking advantage of quality purchase discounts and forward buys, supporting the firm's customer service policies, meeting changing market conditions and uncertainties (e.g. seasonality, demand fluctuations, competition), overcoming the time and space differences that exist between producers and customers, providing temporary storage of material to be disposed or recycled (i.e. reverse logistics). Warehousing seems to have an impact on the following performance measures: time, flexibility and cost. The impact on time is, because, according to Bowersox et al., (2002) regular availability of stocks on warehouses allow firms to decrease their lead times. The consequence of this is an increase on customer satisfaction. Warehousing is also associated with flexibility since the storage of products allows firms not only to increase their operational flexibility but also its responsiveness to costumers' requirements. An important decision for many firms is the criteria for locating the warehouse facilities. Cost factors are prevalent in the decision making models. Resources such as skilled labour are also emphasized in some of the models. Another dominant factor is what might be named as accessibility, meaning infrastructure and availability of transportation modes (Alberto, 2000). Alberto (2000) also gives a high concentration on time and reliability related considerations. This includes the proximity of customers manufacturing facilities and suppliers. On the other hand from the point of view of Ozalp et al. (2010) the way warehouses are managed will contribute to a reduction on costs and time; accuracy and timely fulfillment of customer orders. Economic benefits of warehousing occur when overall logistics

costs are reduced. As Bowersox et al., (2002) stated warehouse in a logistical system reduces overall transportation cost by an amount greater than required investment and operational cost, and then total cost will be reduced. Warehouse service can provide benefits through enhanced revenue generation. When a warehouse is primarily justified on service, the supporting rationale is that sales can be increased, in part, by such logistical performance. Establishing a warehouse to service a specific market may increase cost but should also increase market sales, revenue, and potentially gross margin. Warehouses can provide service as a result of spot stocking, full line stocking, product support, and market presence (Bowersox et al., 2002).

2.3.6 Logistics Information System

Logistics information systems (LISs) are the means by which firms capture, analyze, and communicate information related to logistics and supply chain management. Logistics is the planning and execution of customer response, inventory management, supply, transportation, and warehousing. Without integrated logistics information system the execution of such activity is unthinkable (Frazelle 2002). Logistics is the task of coordinating material flow and information flow across the supply chain (Harrison and van Hoek 2008). So that logistics information system is very important to facilitate such material and information flow in an organization.

Gunasekaran et al. (2007) note that logistics function incorporates the smooth flow of materials, products and information throughout the organizations supply chain that must be supported by Information Systems. Information is the engine that drives the logistics cycle; without information, the logistics system would not run smoothly. According to Ketikidis et al. (2008) the lack of information sharing is noted to be the main bottleneck for maximizing the organizations profit. Thus, different LIS technologies have been adopted to manage accurately logistics operation. Certainly adopting LIS could provide an organization a competitive advantage in order to differentiate in the industry it competes. Information technology is a major source of improved productivity as well as competitiveness. Somuyiwa (2010) stated that companies are now equipped to make effective use of data, from warehouse management systems, which contain information on supplier/customer, warehouse inventory levels and key customer ordering patterns and transportation management systems which facilitates information pertaining to the location of important supply chain assets, such as products or vehicles is typically stored. Technologies which have wide spread logistics applications such as organizational management system, driver information system, fleet management system,

customs operations system, customer relations management system, warehouse management system, Barcode system, RFID (Radio-Frequency Identification), EDI (Electronic Data Interchange), provide great utilities for logistics operations (Aydm, 2014).

Electronic Data Interchange, reduces logistics labor cost and material cost associated with papers, reduces communication and also clerical cost, Artificial Intelligence or Expert Systems Logistics expert systems increase a firm's return on assets, communication, logistics performance through faster and wide spread communication is enhanced by information technology. Bar Coding and Scanning, Collection and exchange of information is very critical for logistical management as well as control, Radio Frequency Identification Device (Frazelle, 2002). As one of its most important functions, an LIS enables logisticians to quickly collect the data needed to make informed decisions, which ultimately improves customer service by minimizing losses and stock imbalances while moving goods and services more efficiently to where they are needed most (Ketikidis et al., 2008). Through well integrated logistics information system firms can save costs through the efficient use of resources, achieve efficiency through the elimination of overlapping resources, perform a proper arrangement of resources, and attain efficiency in processes. Furthermore, LIS brings collaboration between marketing, logistics and production departments, between the supply plans of suppliers and production plans of manufacturers and also between the production plans of manufacturers and the distribution plans of wholesalers and retailers through the customers (Bae, 2016). Logistics Information systems fasten communication between managers in the supply chain, information technology integration enhances quality, reduces time and costs, enhances competitiveness and generates future growth and that information sharing aids replacement of inventories aiding in fast decision making. The flow of information through logistics information systems helps in reducing the cost of logistics operations due to increased coordination between the various activities across the supply chain (Gacuru, 2015).

Managers grasp market information and customer needs through LIS, share the information with other departments and structure logistics processes to reflect customer needs. LIS plays a role in promoting information sharing from the internal and external view points of firms and, as a result, organization can improve customer service through structuring collaborative service processes with suppliers from the externally (Bae, 2016). The successful integration of

information within an organization is a powerful enabler for reduced costs; increased productivity; and improved customer service as well firm performance (Gacuru, 2015).

2.4 Logistics Performance

Marketing experts have recognized that for developing a position of sustainable competitive advantage, a major source is superior logistics performance. Business can only compete and survive either by winning a cost advantage or by providing superior value and benefit to the customer (Mansidao and Coelho, 2014). Literatures have recognized the importance of logistics performance for improving the well-functioning of business processes of an organization and across supply chains (Green et. al, 2008; Mansidao and Coelho, 2014). There are a considerable amount of works of articles on the relationship between logistics performance and organizational performance for instance the work of Neely, Gregory, and Platts, (2005) who confirmed that the performance of logistics activities can have an impact on organizational performance.

However, for logistics management to be considered contributing to a firm's performance, logistics performance needed to be measured (Keebler and Plank, 2009). Waters, (2003) have defined logistics performance as the extent to which goals such as sales growth, job security and working conditions, customer satisfaction, product availability, cost-efficiency, profitability, social responsibility, on-time delivery, keeping promises, low loss and damage, fair prices for inputs, and flexibility are achieved. Due to the lack of any universally-accepted definition for performance in the logistics performance, literature offers many ideas about the dimensions that have to be incorporated into a conceptualization of logistics performance. Fugate (2010) has been attempted to determine logistics success through the combination of efficiency, effectiveness, and differentiation (as cited in Addishiwot, 2016). However, this measure has raised some criticism under the argument that efficiency and effectiveness of a determined action does not allow measuring the performance of all the process, obtaining in this case only a biased performance measurement (Keeble and plank, 2009). In contrast, other authors defends that logistics performance measurement should fall on the whole process. On deciding the performance measures, firms must combine several measures between general performance measures, which are financial-accounting nature (sales, profit, return on investments), and measures should involve directly related to the logistics process and cross functions, in other words operational ones (Waters, 2003). Hence, it is necessary to include that measures of operational nature should prevail in a logistics' performance measurement.

According to Frazelle since businesses compete on the basis of financial performance, productivity performance, quality performance and cycle time performance logistics performance measures should fall into those four areas. The recommended measures also point to the need for single-point accountability for logistics performance in value, cost, productivity, quality, and time (Frazelle, 2002). Christopher (2011) considers time, cost and quality as three key performance measures which should form part of any logistics Performance measurement system. This is because these measures contribute more than proportionally to the success or failure of a firm. In this context, the logistics performance measures proposed in this research is: cost, quality, time and flexibility. These four measures are also proposed by (Neely et al., 2005) and they pointed out that the generic terms quality, time, cost and flexibility encompass a variety of different dimensions. As stated by Lawrence, Fredendall and Ed (2001) value is the function of quality, as perceived by the customer; the delivery of the product which could represent the actual lead time, variance in the lead time, or the method of delivery; and the firm's flexibility and that customers perceive these benefits of the product in relation to the cost of the product. These metrics reflect the new competitive priority of firms, that is agility, is because through the utilization of these four measures (cost, quality, time and flexibility) organizations can assess the logistics response capability of firms to the new environment faced by firms and also to the levels of wastes (in terms of time, resources, and quality) that exist all over the firms (Lawrence et al., 2001).

2.4.1 Logistics Cost

Total logistics costs consider the full array of costs to make products available to the final consumer, namely transport; warehousing and transshipment. The goal of distribution is to make the finished products available to the customer at a low cost and with a high customer service level (Bowersox et al., 2002). Transportation costs remain the dominant consideration as they account for about half of the logistic costs. Inventory carrying costs are also significant with a share of about one fifth of total costs. They include the costs of holding goods in inventory (capital costs, warehousing, depreciation, insurance, taxation, and obsolescence) and are commonly expressed as a share of the inventory value. Labor costs involve the physical handling of goods, including tasks such as packaging and labeling (Rodrigue, 2012). Put another way common elements in total logistics cost categorize inventory carrying costs, transportation costs, lot quantity costs, warehousing costs and order processing, administration costs and information

costs. In logistics the aim is to reach as low total costs as possible while at the same time offering the required level of customer service. This point out that focus should not be on achieving the highest customer service possible but rather on offering the customers the service level they demand (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008).

As demonstrated by Mansidao and Coelho (2014) this is because a very high level of customer service will lead to extremely high costs, without a substantial increase in revenues. This characteristic reflects one aspect of the conflicting goals that exists within the area of logistics. Frazelle, (2002) explained that Logistics costs often shift in opposite directions or in other words are in conflict. As inventory is reduced transport costs rise because smaller quantities are shipped more frequently. On the other hand, as we reduce transport costs by shipping in larger quantities by less expensive modes, inventory levels in the system rise. However these conflicts would be alleviated through efficient logistics management which by improving the logistics and physical distribution, the transportation cost (or as a whole logistics cost) will be decreased while achieving the desired service level and at the same time cost efficiency for whole of the system. Christopher (2011) puts another perspective to logistics when he refers to it as a source of competitive advantage. He argues that successful companies have either a cost advantage or a value advantage or both of them. By value advantage the author refers to the ideathat a product or service has to be unique for the customer not to choose the cheapest competitor instead. Furthermore, logistics can provide a number of different ways to reduce the costs by increasing the efficiency and productivity. The optimal position for acompany is to be both a cost and service leader which can be achieved by having both ahigh value advantage and a high cost advantage. Managing logistics process saves significant amount of costs and enables to provide a competitive price in the market.

2.4.2 Logistics Service Quality

The quality of logistics services is better perceived by customers and users of the network than the quality of the corresponding physical infrastructure. Quality of logistics services measures the overall competenceof the logistics services provided by an organizations logistics process/the logistics system (Rodrigue, 2012). Achieving logistics excellence requires continuous improvement in reliability, responsiveness and well-functioning support services. It was recognized that the quality of the distribution service could have a significant impact on sales, market share, and long-term customer loyalty. Quality of logistics service addresses the process

of handing over products and services into the hands of end-customers. Only after this process has been completed does the product/service reach its full value (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008).

Quality is the most visible aspect of logistics performance. Defects, incorrect quantities and wrong items delivered are symptoms of quality problems in the logistics processes that are all too apparent to the end customer (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008).

The logistics quality parameters error rate on invoices, delivery notes and other customer communications, user friendly documentation Percentage of orders delivered complete, and the variability against target percentage of defects, the variability against target and large number of logistics quality failures are from this source (Frazelle, 2002). As stated by Muslimin et al. (2015) Logistics is expected to provide a better improvement of the quality incoming flows of materials and outcome delivery and the accuracy of the amount of raw material by the company. In other words, the logistics process should optimize the flow of goods in order to maintain quality, on time delivery and satisfaction. Therefore, the capability of logistics to manage both these flows will enhance the value added and have an impact on maintain the business performance (Muslimin et al., 2015). A fundamental quality issue in logistics is the ability to comply with levels of planned inventory availability and performance. Beyond service standards, quality compliance involves a capability and willingness to rapidly provide accurate customer information regarding logistical operations and order status. The notion of the perfect order is that desired customer service capability, in terms of availability and performance, should be synchronized to achieve target service goals each and every time (Christopher, 2011). Bowersox, et al., (2002) demonstrated that quality is not just about meeting target pick accuracy, or target defect levels. In many logistics situations, quality of logistics service is about selecting the right quantity of the right product in the right sequence in response to customer orders. Logistics carries out this activity in the best way, in which, customers can receive quality goods and services confidently with the appropriate speed and quality and also with the least price. A product that is produced in superior quality does not have any value until it arrives at the hands of the customers without any defect. Well integrated logistics system is required to ensure that the product achieves its intended desired value.

2.4.3 Time to Deliver

The timeliness of shipments in reaching destination measures the reliability of shipment delivery times. Delivery times depend on the nature of the product, planning and supply chain

management, logistics services, and distance to customers and suppliers. Long lead time is not a problem if delivery is predictable and demand is stable. However, if there is uncertainty about future demand, long lead time is costly, even if the customer knows exactly when the merchandise will arrive (Rodrigue, 2012). While the length of the lead time affects volumes, time variability mainly affects the efficiency of logistics systems. The more variable the delivery time, the more buffer stocks are needed. Thus, even if average lead times are low, a high rate of variability can render a supplier uncompetitive and can be more damaging than having long, but predictable, lead times (Bowersox, et al., 2002).

As of Christopher (2011) emphasizes that short lead times can be a major source of competitive advantage. However, he also points out that the reliability of the customer order lead time is equally important which leads on to the next customer service element. As explained by Frazelle (2002) time can be used as a tool to reach lower costs and better customer service. Keeping the time aspect in mind is becoming more important in order to survive in a competitive market. Furthermore, timely delivery is an appropriate measurement since it is easy to measure and easy for the people in the organization to understand. Lawrence, Fredendall and Ed (2001) added that it is impossible to reach an overall efficient in logistics system if it is not time efficient. When discussing delivery time related logistics performance indicators mention three types; customer order lead time, lead time and inventory turnover rate. lead time refers to as the time it takes for a product or matter to go through any given part of the total flow. on the other hand, time-based metrics were to be employed then the focus could be on cycle-time reduction, set-up time reduction and other measures that encourage agile practices (Christopher, 2011). On Time delivery then becomes an important factor for achieving a competitive advantage. Traditional purchasing based on long-term forecasts implies high risk, and it is difficult to make a good forecast. One way to handle this is by Quick Response strategies, where an important aim is to shorten the lead times and to reduce inventory levels in the supply chain (Rodrigue, 2012). One of the major advantages of a time-based approach to measure logistics process over one based on cost or quality is the ease with which time is understood as a determinable. While cost and quality are open to differences in interpretation, time is an absolute measure (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008).

2.4.4 Logistics Flexibility

The many different facets of logistical performance requirements make operational design a complex task as an operating structure must offer a balance of performance, cost, and flexibility (Bowersox, et al., 2002). Flexibility involves the ability of the logistics system to accommodate special situations and unusual or unexpected customer requests. For example, the standard pattern for servicing a customer may be to ship full-trailer quantities to a customer's warehouse.

However, from time to time, the customer may desire to have shipments of smaller quantities made direct to individual retail locations. In many ways the essence of logistical excellence rests in the ability to be flexible (Bowersox et al., 2002). Lack of flexibility is a major contributor to poor quality of logistics service to the end-customer. The rationale behind small batches is that they can reduce total cost across a supply chain, such as removing the waste of overproduction (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008). The flexibility measure of logistics evaluates the capability of providing special services for orders such as processing back-orders, providing substitute products, expediting orders, and providing faster transportation.

The flexibility measure must record the relative effort involved in the changes and the organization's ability to respond (Virolainen, 1991). Continuous information exchange regarding availability and delivery reduces uncertainty for the total supply chain and creates the opportunity for maximum flexibility. With fast, dependable order response, inventory can be committed as required, resulting in increased turnover and improved availability (Muslimin et al., 2015). Flexibility is the key to providing high-level basic customer service while maintaining sufficient operating capacity to meet and exceed key customer expectations. Not only do customers want shorter lead times, they are also looking for flexibility and increasingly customized solutions. In other words, the supplier has to be able to meet the precise needs of customers in less time than ever before (Christopher, 2011). Logistics solutions therefore create flexibility, speed and reliability in the supply chain. This also means that, whenever possible, simple solutions can be implemented, creating lower inventory, lower transport costs. Logistics flexibility (to accommodate increases and decreases in the flow of goods) addresses the ability to adjust to changes in customer demands (Rodrigue, 2012). Flexibility also implies that the organization is close to the customer, hearing the voice of the market and quick to interpret the demand signals it receives. The logistics challenge is therefore concerned with speed of response and flexibility to changing demand. Logistical system must be designed to maintain flexibility

and be capable of adjusting to counter a competitive activity at any specific point in time (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008). This requires a clear perspective of just what customer service is and how it should be deployed. To exploit flexibility, an organization needs to achieve a high level of logistical process integration (Christopher, 2011).

2.5 Organizational Performance

Firm performance comprised the actual output or results of an organization as measured against its intended outputs (or goals and objectives), it involved the recurring activities to establish organizational goals, monitor progress toward the goals, and make adjustments to achieve those goals more effectively and efficiently (Richard et al., 2009). Ultimately, the success of every organization depends on customer satisfaction. If it does not satisfy customers, it is unlikely to survive in the long term, let alone make a profit, have high return on assets, add shareholder value, or achieve any other measure of success. So organizations must deliver products that satisfy customers. Unfortunately, customers judge products by a whole series of factors (Waters, 2003). Schramm and Morschett, (2006) argues that marketing performance (sales and market share growth) and financial performance (return on investment and profit growth) are consequences of performance of logistics activities. The main mission of Logistics is “the process of strategically managing the acquisition, movement and storage of materials, parts and finished inventory and the related information flows through the organization and its marketing channel in such a way that current and future profitability is maximized through the cost-effective fulfillment of orders (Christopher, 2011). Management of logistics activities can affect a firm’s sales revenue, return on investment and other balance sheet items. Logistics customer service and logistics cost efficiency significantly determines a company’s sales revenue and profit. Pipeline management, invoice accuracy, just in time logistics inventory, and asset utilization, has also determined the firms (cash, net receivables, inventory, and fixed assets) capital employed hence its return on investment (Christopher, 2011). Hence the aim of logistics can be phrased adding value for the products by providing place and time utility for customers. Through this way logistics enhances the firms’ capability of achieving market and financial oriented goals. According to Richard et al. (2009) firm performance encompasses three specific areas of firm outcomes: financial performance (profits, return on assets, return on investment); market performance (sales, market share); and, customer satisfaction/value added (Richard, *et al.*, 2009). Financial performance measures are more likely to reflect the assessment of a firm by factors

outside of the firm's boundaries. These measures would include conventional indicators of business performance, such as market share, return on investment, and sales growth (Stock, Greis and Kasarda, 2000). Marketing performance reflects the organization's ability to increase sales and expand market share as compared to its competitors (Green et al., 2008). Financial performance reflects an organization's profitability and return on investment as compared to its competitors (Green et al., 2008). Based on this market share, the growth in market share, the growth in sales, return on investment, growth in return on investment, profit margin on sales and overall competitive position proposed for this study which has both natures of financial and market oriented objectives as a measure of organizational performance.

2.6 Empirical Review of Studies

Logistics has traditionally been considered necessary for connecting production and consumption. From this perspective, a company's logistics function was seen only as a generator of costs with no capacity for differentiation (Ballou, 2007). However, now researchers arrived that the logistics activities within a business organization attempt to satisfy customers through achieving the time and location related market challenges and also through the cost of the service provided as well as the quality, taking into consideration customers needs and purchase power and has the capability to impact firms overall profitability. There have been various studies conducted by different researchers on the area of logistics practices, logistics performance and its contribution for companies' performance. For instance Mukolwe and Wanyoike, (2015) conducted a research with the objective of assessing logistics management practices on operational efficiency of Mumias Sugar Company Limited, in Kenya. The study considers Information flow, Warehousing, Distribution, Transport Management as logistics activities and reveals that effective management of information flow improves the company's internal and external processes; Automation of warehousing activities greatly enhances accuracy, speed of operations and reduces wastage; Transport management practices allows faster and cost effective flow of goods and raw materials thus improving operational efficiency. However their study also found that physical distribution is not significant in explaining the relationship between logistics management practices and Operational Efficiency. Another study by Kirui and Nondi (2017) investigated the effects of logistics management on the organization performance of shipping firms in Mombasa, Kenya. The study was sought to address the effect of warehousing management, inventory management and transportation management, reverse logistics

management on organizational performance of shipping firms in Mombasa. The study was confirmed that components such as warehouse management, inventory management, transport management and reverse logistics were highly practiced in most of the firms studied and had a positive impact on organization performance. Ristovska, Kozuharov and Petkovski (2017), had been worked on impact of company's logistics management including transportation, warehousing, packaging, inventory and information management to the efficiency and effectiveness on different companies in the Republic of Macedonia. Their finding showed that the necessity of logistics managers to optimally manage all logistics activities in order to gain increased business efficiency, customer satisfaction and competitiveness. They added that reduction of the cost of each logistics activity influences the total amount of costs and enhances company's performance. Other researchers also found that there is strong relationship between logistics and financial performance. Muslimin, Hadi, and Ardiansyah (2015) when they examined the relationship between logistics practice and financial performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Indonesia Central Sulawesi Province. They were take logistics cost, flexibility, reliability, security, service quality as an independent variable and financial performance as dependent. Their result indicated that logistics cost and service quality have positive relationship to SMEs' financial performance. On the other hand flexibility, reliability and security have negative correlation to SMEs' financial performance.

Shang and Marlow (2007), examined that the relationships between logistics competency, logistics performance, and financial performance in Taiwan. Their study identified four logistics competencies; integration and knowledge competency, customer focused logistics competency, measurement competency, and agility competency. Their finding confirmed that logistics competency has significantly related to logistics performance but not significantly associated with financial performance, and logistics performance has positively associated with financial performance. They also conclude that logistics competency has an indirect effect on financial performance through logistics performance. Dubey (2008) has been conducted a study on improving firm performance through logistics activities in Dehradun, India. The objective of this study was empirically testing the impact of a set of logistics activities on firm's performance. The study was taken logistics activities as Warehousing, Inventory control, Handling, Packaging and Picking. This study confirms that logistics activities have positive impact on firm's performance in terms of sales, market share, profitability and growth. Gacuru (2015) investigated

the factors affecting efficiency in logistics performance of trading and distribution firms in Kenya logistics performance as measured in Cost reduction, Quality of product/service, Timeliness of delivery, Competitive advantage. The study comes with the finding that information technology, level of competence and business to business relationship affects the efficiency of logistics performance in trade and distribution firms.

Bagshaw (2017) examined the relationship between logistics management and performance of 122 selected firms within Rivers State, Nigeria. The findings of the study showed that logistics management has an influence on the rate of production output, market share and profitability. Furthermore, inventory and warehouse management helps in eliminating production short-outs; enhances effectiveness of the production system and improves performance of manufacturing firms. The relationship between supply chain management strategy, marketing, logistics and company performance for breweries in Serbia have been analyzed by (Ilic and Tesic, 2016) and Logistics and supply chain management practices have associated benefits such as lower cost, higher quality, better customer service and improved competitive advantage. Furthermore, the analysis confirmed that logistics service/product quality, logistics costs, logistics flexibility and timeliness have a significant and positive impact on financial and market performance of company. Gunasekaran and Ngai (2003) identified logistics activities as Transportation, Warehousing management, inventory management, Order processing, logistics Information systems, and Packaging when he conducted a case study on the successful management of a small logistics company on Tolam Logistics third-party logistics (3PL) company in Hong Kong. His finding shows that reduction in logistics costs and improvement in customer services will help bring a company to realize the full potential of its value-added and to gain a significant competitive advantage. Odhiambo et al., (2017) conducted a study on effect of logistics activities on performance of agro processing firms in uasin gishu county, Kenya. The study concludes that the constructs under study were like transport management, material handling, packaging and information and communication technology are key in enhancing the performance of agro processing firms in Uasin Gishu County. Thus the finding of the study provides an absolute support to the suggestion that logistics activities be recognized as a significant precursor for the performance of firms. It is apparent that efficient and effective management of logistic activities for organizations is an important ingredient to satisfy the various needs of supply chain management and in return eliciting high performance of the agro

processing industry .While there are other factors crucial for organization performance, From the results; Their study recommends that industry should pay more attention in addressing transport management, material handling , packaging and information communication in order to increase the performance of the industry.

2.7 Logistics Practice in Ethiopian Case

The study conducted by Fekadu (2013) on logistics practices of Ethiopia was mainly focused on the transportation and customer service practices using general attributes of infrastructure, performance, information system, human resources, business and political environments. The finding indicate that Ethiopian logistics system is characterized by poor logistics practices and lack of coordination of goods transport, low level of development of logistics infrastructure and inadequate fleets of freight vehicles in number and age, damage and quality deterioration of goods while handling, transporting and storage. Another study by Melkamu (2016) who give special emphasis on logistics practices in Ethiopian medium and large leather footwear manufacturing firms and his analysis show that most of the respondent firms have not started to practice logistics activities to a great extent. His study considers logistics practices as customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management and warehouse management. His finding indicates even though correct identification of all materials in stock, effective implementation of purchase order processing, sending and receiving of electronic communication between firms and suppliers, and creation of long term relationship with the suppliers are well practiced by the firm; Achieving the lowest inventory driven cost, frequent measurement and analysis of suppliers' performance, measuring the transport performance are poorly practiced by the firms and Foreign currency shortages, higher taxes, lack of integrated system and long lead time in ports are the major challenges of logistics facing footwear firms. A study by Tura Kaso and Efa Gobena (2017) on the role of logistics on agribusiness firms in Ethiopia indicates that due to poor logistics management in agribusiness firms are vulnerable to high operation costs. Their finding revealed that even though there are some study deals with logistics, there are no Contemporary studies and research points to the logistics in manufacturing firm as it is perceived that firm could maximize on their produce and also potentially increase their revenue in the process. Their research finding also suggest that manufacturing firms couldn't achieve their market and financial objectives like revenue growth, increase market share other than using effective and efficient logistic system. The effect of logistics management

practice on performance of fafa foods manufacturing Share Company was investigated by Afomeya (2016); the study analyzed the logistic performance from the external customer point of view and her study considers individual logistics performance indicators such as product quality, logistics responsiveness, product variety, delivery time and logistic cost on performance. The finding indicated there is strong link between logistics practice and performance from the perspective of customer satisfaction.

2.8 Conceptual Framework

Based on the review of related literatures the following conceptual framework is constructed in which this particular research is governed. The figure below shows the relationship between variables under study; the relationship between dependent and independent variables demonstrated conceptually.

Figure 2.1: The research framework adapted from (Mwangangi, 2016; KiruiandNondi, 2017) and modified by the researcher.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 INTRODUCTION

This Chapter deals with research methodology. This is a significant part of the research which justifies the reliability and strength of the data that were collected in the research. The Chapter presents the description of the study area, the research design, samples and sampling procedures, type of data and method used during data collection, data analysis both qualitative and quantitative data, validity and reliability of the data, consideration of ethical issues as in the following sections.

3.2 Description of the Study Area

This research was conducted on kombolcha textile Share Company which is located in south wello amhara region; 380 km a way from Addis Ababa to the north. The study was aimed at analyzing the current logistics practices of the company and the effect that logistics practice has on the performance of kombolcha textile Share Company. The main reason that KTSC is selected as the case company for this research was since KTSC is textile manufacturing firm which sources cotton as its core raw martial from different parts of the country and distributes its product mix to local and foreign markets. In doing this logistics has a great role on the company's daily operations and the overall organizations performance. The concept of logistics management is broad and the company manages some of these activities under the division of procurement and property control. Therefore, the researcher has selected customer service, , inventory planning, supply/procurement process transportation, warehousing, logistics information system and logistics performance (cost, time, quality and flexibility); organizational performance (Market share, The growth in market share,the growth in sales, return on investment, Growth in return on investment, Profit margin on sales and overall competitive position) the areas to be touched in this study.

3.3 Research Design

Designing a study helps the researcher to plan and implement the study in a way that will help the researcher to obtain intended results, thus increasing the chances of obtaining information that could be associated with the real situation (Burns and Grove 2001). Creswell (2012) stated that Cross-sectional research design has the advantage of measuring current attitudes or practices

and Program evaluation. It also provides information in a short amount of time, such as the time required for administering the survey and collecting the information. And the essence of this research is to analyze the current logistics practices and its correlation with firm performance. Hence, Based on the number of contact with the study population this research is cross sectional. Besides this the study is also associational in design because there is the intention to establish the relationship between dependent and independent variable of the study. Therefore, the researcher had been used Cross-sectional research design to assess existing logistics practices, to test association between logistics practices and logistics performance on one hand and logistics practices with organizational performance, and finally the relationship between logistics performance measures and organizational performance of kombolcha textile Share Company.

3.4 Research Approach

The three methods that are commonly implemented in a research are quantitative, qualitative and mixed, where one of them is not better than the others, all of this depends on how the researcher want to do a research of study (Creswell, 2012). Creswell (2012) asserted that quantitative research is a type of educational research in which the researcher decides what to study, asks specific, narrow questions, collects numeric (numbered) data from participants, analyzes these numbers using statistics, and conducts the inquiry in an unbiased, objective manner. Besides it also helps in examining and describing a cause and effect interactions among those variables (Dawson, 2002). Variables can be defined as attributes or characteristics of individuals, groups, or sub-groups of individuals (Creswell, 2009). Whereas Qualitative research explores attitudes, behavior and experiences through such methods as interviews or focus groups (Dawson, 2002). Qualitative research is a means for exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. The process of research involves emerging questions and procedures, data typically collected in the participant's setting, data analysis inductively building from particulars to general themes, and the researcher making interpretations of the meaning of the data (Creswell, 2009).

In qualitative research as it concerned on attitudes, behavior and experiences which are important, fewer people take part in the research (Dawson, 2002). As it is observed neither is better than the other, they are just different and both have their strengths and weaknesses. Many researchers believe that mixed approach is a good way of approaching research as it enables you to counteract the weaknesses in both qualitative and quantitative research (Dawson, 2002).

Hence this research have been employed both qualitative and quantitative approaches so as to offset the weaknesses of each. Quantitative approach helps researchers to test relationships between variables. Quantitative data that has been used in this study was collected from primary sources through questionnaire and qualitative data was gathered through semi-structured interview.

3.5 Sampling and Sampling Techniques

3.5.1 Target Population

According to Hair *et al.* (2010), target population is said to be a specified group of people or object for which questions can be asked or observed made to develop required data structures and information. Therefore, for this study, the target populations are employees of kombolcha textile Share Company, particularly those their function is related with logistics activities.

3.5.2 Sampling Techniques

Sampling is the process of selecting the right individuals, objects, or events for study and selecting a sufficient number of elements from the population, so that a study of the sample and an understanding of its properties or characteristics would make it possible for researcher to generalize such properties or characteristics to the population elements (Sekaran, 2003).

For the purpose of this study, the researcher was used probability and non-probability sampling technique. From probability sampling technique random stratified sampling is used to choose the proportion of samples from selected departments (strata) which have chosen purposively based on their direct and indirect link with logistics activities. Then the questionnaire was distributed purposively to sampled respondents. The target population for the study is classified into six strata (classes) based on the departments and section in the organization which is directly or indirectly related with logistics activities of the organization. Then the samples were selected from each stratum/class according to their proportion to the total population. Since the information required for the study needs different people who have knowledge and awareness about logistics practices, logistics performance and organizational performance of the company, so that stratified sampling technique were used to have the right proportion of people from every concerned department. The departments considered as strata, from which data had been collected, were: procurement and property control, top management (General Manager and Operations Deputy G/Manager), finance department, production department (spinning, weaving

and garment), marketing department and quality assurance service. Out of 1058 employees in production (i.e., spinning, weaving and garment) 1000 employees were not considered in the sample selection since they are less involved in logistics activities and only 58 supervisors and foremen were included in the sample selection who supposed to have awareness about logistics activities.

3.5.3 Sample Size

Creswell (2012) stated that, the larger the sample size, the less the potential error is that the sample will be different from the population. Therefore, so as to get the required data; sample determination method developed by Taro Yamane's (1973) is preferred to be used by the researcher as a method to determine a sample size (cited by Biniyam, 2016). This formula is working with a finite population and if the population size is known, the Yamane formula for determining the sample size is given by:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n= corrected sample size, N = population size, and e = Margin of error e = 0.05 based on the research condition.

Table: 3.1 numbers of classes with the corresponding population

No.	Departments or strata	Number of population in each class
1.	Top management	4
2.	finance department	29
3.	procurement and property control	28
4.	production department	58
5.	marketing department	10
6.	quality assurance service	95
	Total population	224

Source: HR department; kombolcha textile share company, 19/10/2017

As we observe from the above table the total target population is 224 and the researcher is 95% level confident that the research will achieve its target which means that the margin of error is 5%. With 5% level of error the sample can be calculated as follows; n= unknown sample and to

be determined N =population and is equal to 224; e =error term and it is considered 5%: Sample size $(n) = \frac{224}{1+224(0.05)^2} = 143.589$ which is close to 144.

Table: 3.2 Number of respondents which will be taken from each class

N o.	Departments or strata	Number of employees in each strata	$\frac{\text{number of } N \text{ in eah class} \times n}{\text{total population}}$
1.	Top management	4	$4 \times 144 \div 224 = 2$
2.	finance department	29	$29 \times 144 \div 224 = 19$
3.	procurement and property control	28	$28 \times 144 \div 224 = 18$
4.	production department	58	$58 \times 144 \div 224 = 37$
5.	marketing department	10	$10 \times 144 \div 224 = 7$
6.	quality assurance service	95	$95 \times 144 \div 224 = 61$
	Total population	224	Sample size=144

Source: own competition, 2018

Finally the proportions which have been taken from each strata is determined as shown above the questionnaires were distributed to those sampled respondents randomly.

3.6 Data Type and Source of Data

Primary data is the information that the researcher finds out by him/herself regarding a specific topic. The main advantage with this type of data is that it is collected with the research's purpose in mind (Biggam, 2008). It is argued that the information resulting primary data is more consistent with the research questions and objectives. Interms of source the researcher was used primary data for the analysis of this study. Those Primary data were collected using self administered questionnaire and via semi structured interview. Interms of measurement the data is also both quantitative and qualitative. The questionnaires were used to gather quantitative data from the selected sample of respondents/ employees or from each stratum (procurement and property control, production, finance, administration, marketing, and quality assurance) of kombolcha textile Share Company. The researcher has backed up the data gathered via questionnaires with the data which was obtained through semi structured interview. The interview was supposed to be conducted with department heads of each considered departments

but two of them were willing to take part the interview and conducted with those supervisors from procurement and property control and marketing department. Secondary data, annual financial statements of the company have been also used for some matters of analysis.

3.7 Data Gathering Technique and Instruments

As stated, questionnaire is a process of asking many people the same questions and examining their answers (Neuman, 2014). The data for this research was collected using questionnaire and through interview. Semi-structured interviewing is perhaps the most common type of interview used in qualitative social research. In this type of interview, the researcher asks the same question and wants to know specific information which can be compared and contrasted with information gained through other instruments (Dawson, 2002). Thus the researcher was prepared semi structured interview questions and conducted an interview with two department heads. The other instrument that was used is questionnaire and it was distributed to sampled respondents from each stratum. The questionnaire is close-ended and prepared by referring various literatures such as (Mwangangi, 2016; Shang, and Marlow, 2007; Neely, Gregory and Platts, 2005; Savitskie, 2003; Ferreira, Leitao and Azevedo, 2007) and has been customized to the research purpose. The close-ended questionnaires can be administered to groups of people simultaneously, since they are less costly and less time consuming than other measuring instruments. The questionnaire is designed with the five Likert-type scale methods which used a range of responses: 'strongly disagree', 'disagree', 'Neutral', 'Agree', and 'Strongly Agree', with a numeric value of 1-5, respectively had been applied. Research instruments designed with likert scale methods are not recommended for regression analysis since multiple regressions requires interval or ratio-level data (Neuman, 2014). Likert scale data to be treating as an interval scale, researchers should develop multiple categories or choices (multiple response rates); in such occasions the errors for treating the Likert scale results as interval data are minimal. Hence; the likert scale having five and more response rates is essential to be considered as an interval scale of measurement and preferable to make regression analysis (Creswell, 2012). The instruments for this study also has response rate ranging from 1=strongly disagree to 5=strongly agree which is more reliable and enough to make the regression.

3.8 Data Analysis

In this study, the collected quantitative data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 to derive descriptive statistics, frequencies, and percentages have

been used. The statistical tools were aligned with the objectives of the research. The qualitative data which was obtained via interview has been narratively analyzed in parallel with quantitative data. Inferential statistics is particularly the Pearson's correlation was used to show the relationship; the strength/degree as well as direction of associations between variables. The other inferential statistics multiple linear regression analysis was used to show interdependence of independent variables and dependent variable. Thus, both the strength of the relationship between variables and the influence of independent on dependent variable and statistical significance is assessed. The following Regression model is developed to show the relationship among logistics practices and logistics performance, logistics practice and organizational performance and finally logistics performance measures and organizational performance:

$$Y_1 = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6 + e$$

$$Y_2 = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + b_4X_4 + b_5X_5 + b_6X_6 + e$$

$$Y_2 = a + b_1A_1 + b_2A_2 + b_3A_3 + b_4A_4 + e$$

Where; Y_1 : represents logistics performance and Y_2 : represents organizational performance; a = the Y intercept when X and A are zero; $b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5,$ and b_6 are the regression weights attached to the variables; X_1 =customer service, X_2 = inventory management, X_3 = supply management, X_4 = transportation, X_5 = warehousing, X_6 = logistics information system and A_1 = logistics cost, A_2 = quality, A_3 = delivery time, A_4 = flexibility; e = is the margin of error considered 5%.

3.9 Validity and Reliability

Reliability is necessary for validity and it is easier to achieve than validity. Although reliability is necessary in order to have a valid measure of a concept, it does not guarantee that a measure will be valid. It is not a sufficient condition for validity. A measure can produce the same result over and over (i.e., it has reliability), but what it measures may not match the definition of the construct (i.e validity) (Neuman, 2003). Neuman, (2003) stated that validity and reliability are usually complementary concepts, but in some situations they conflict with each other. Sometimes as validity increases reliability is difficult to attain. This happens when the construct has a highly abstract and not easily observable definition. Therefore; it is essential to make precise and observable definition of the measures.

3.9.1 Reliability

The reliability of a measure indicates the extent to which it is without bias (error free) and hence ensures consistent measurement across time and across the various items in the instrument. In other words, the reliability of a measure is an indication of the stability and consistency with which the instrument measures the concept and helps to assess the goodness of a measure (Sekaran, 2003). As Neuman, (2003) pointed out reliability of instruments can be improved through clearly conceptualize the Constructs, use a precise level of measurement, use multiple indicators and Use of pilot-tests. The internal consistency of the instruments of this research was tested using Cronbach’s coefficient alpha reliability test by collecting data from four respondents from the case company before the actual data is collected as depicted in the following table.

Table 3.3-Reliability test results

Logistics practices	Cronbach’s Alpha	No. of Items
Customer Service	.717	8
Inventory Management	.701	8
Supply management	.717	9
Transportation management	.877	8
Warehouse management	.863	9
Logistics information system	.763	10
Logistics Performance		
Cost/price	.743	8
Quality	.755	8
Time to deliver	.827	7
Flexibility	.829	8
Organizational performance	.816	7

Source: Field survey, 2018

According to George and Mallery (2003), Chronbanch’s Alpha is an indicator of degree of internal consistency of scales. The higher the coefficient the higher degree of consistency denotes; >0.9-Excellent, >0.8-Good, >0.7-Acceptable, >0.6-Quesstionable, >0.5-Poor, <0.5-Unacceptable. Therefore, as shown in the table 3.3 above, the result of the reliability test revealed that the items in the questionnaire exhibited Chronbanch Alpha rate more than enough to be called consistent or acceptable.As clearly shown in the above table, all the scales used to measure the constructs of this particular study scored calculated Cronbanch’s alpha values that range from the lowest value of 0.701 to the highest value of 0.877.

3.9.2 Validity

Validity refers to whether or not the measurement collects the data required to answer the research question. Internal validity refers to the confidence that can be placed in causal inferences. External validity refers to the possibility of expanding any claims of causality from the group or sample being studied to the population that the group represents that the same effect will be found in another group and/or in other contexts (Somekh and Lewin, 2005). A test is considered valid for a particular purpose if it does, in fact, measure what it purports to measure (Swerdlik, 2009). According to Neuman, (2003) internal validity of a research instrument is viewed from face, content, and concurrent. Face validity: logical link between objectives and research questions by the judgment of others; content validity: captures the entire meaning of the construct; concurrent validity: association and agreement of indicators with preexisting measures. The researcher reviews and examining prior studies that have reported scores and use of the instrument to incorporate relevant constructs and items to ensure face, content and concurrent validity of the instruments and have made an effort so as to establish logical link between objectives and research questions. In addition to this the research questionnaire was detected and evaluated by the advisor for logical link, content coverage, and agreement with preexisting literatures. External validity concerned about the extent to which the research findings can be generalized to other population. Since this study is conducted in a single company it is difficult to generalize the result to other companies beyond the case company and this will be the limitation of this research.

3.10 Ethical issues

The study adhered to all ethical issues. Ethical issues are crucial in research since they guide the researcher on what is allowable and what is not and thus were mandatory for the researcher to observe. Ethical issues included informed consent, confidentiality of information, privacy and anonymity of respondent (Leedy and Ormrod, 2010). The respondents' willingness has been obtained to fill the questionnaire and participate in the interview. The collected data is also used only for this research purpose. In addition research clearance was obtained from the department of logistics and supply chain management, college of business and economics, Aksum University and the department's official letter also gets approved by the case company.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Introduction

So far it is stated that the general objective of this research is to describe logistics practices and investigating the relationship between logistics practice, logistics performance and firm performance with particular emphasis on kombolcha textile Share Company. So that, the effort was to achieve this objective, and so as to answer questions formulated in chapter one. Therefore, as it can be understood from the title, this chapter is all about presentation, analysis and interpretation of the research findings. Thus, in the following sections of the chapter both descriptively and inferentially found results of the study is presented, analyzed and interpreted using different statistical and judgmental procedures. Descriptive statistics analysis such as frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were calculated to present the general information about respondents and respective measurements of logistics practices, logistics performance and organizational performance. Inferential Statistical measurement tools such as; correlation and regression analysis were used to test the relationship among logistics practices, logistics performance and organizational performance. Narrative analysis was also employed so as to analyze qualitatively found data in parallel with quantitative results.

4.2 Response Rate

A total of 144 questionnaires were distributed in person to the designated respondents only 128 questionnaires were properly filled and used in the analysis. From the remaining 16 questionnaires; 7 were not returned at all, and 9 were not correctly filled. Therefore, the overall response rate was 88.9% and the result is depicted below in table 4.1.

Table 4.1-Response Rate

No.	Name of Departments	No. of questionnaires distributed	No. of questionnaires collected	No. of questionnaires lost
1.	Top management	2	2	0
2.	marketing	7	7	0
3.	Finance	19	19	0
4.	production	37	31	6

5.	Procurement	18	18	0
6.	Quality assurance	61	51	10
	Total	144	128	16

Source: Field Survey, 2018

4.3 Respondent Profile

The information regarding profile of respondents considered in the study was the respondent's gender, Age, level of education, their experience in the organization, department/work unit and the result is illustrated in below table 4.2.

Gender

The respondents were asked to show their gender, this was expected to understand the gender characteristics of the respondents. The results as in the below table 4.2 shows that majority of the respondent were male at 59.4% while female was 40.6% showing that comparatively most of the respondents participated in this study were male.

Table 4.2-Profile of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Valid Percent
Gender		
Male	76	59.4
Female	52	40.6
Respondents age group		
18-24	8	6.3
25-30	54	42.2
31-35	35	27.3
36-40	17	13.3
Over 41	14	10.9
Respondents level of education		
College diploma	36	28.1
First degree	89	69.5
Second degree	3	2.3
Years Respondents stayed in the organization		
Less than 2 years	7	5.5

2-5 years	52	40.6
6-10 years	46	35.9
Over 10 years	22	17.2

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Respondents' Age Group

The respondents were asked to indicate their ages in number and the researcher grouped their ages in to 18-24 years, 25-30 years, 31-35 years, 36-40 and over 41 years. As it is depicted from table 4.2 about 6.3% of the respondents were between 18-24, 42.2% of the respondents were between 25 and 30, 27.3% of them were ages of 31-35, 13.3% of the respondents were between 36 and 40, and 10.9% of the respondents were ages of above 41. The result indicated that most of the workers (82.8%) in kombolcha textile Share Company are between the ages of 25 and 40. This is significant for the company's overall productivity since they are under the productive age group.

Respondents' Level of Education

The respondents were asked to indicate the highest level of education they have attained. As indicated in table 4.2 above about 28.1% of the respondents have college diploma, 69.5% of the respondents have first degree and 2.3% of them have second degree. The result convinced that close 70% of the company's (KTSC) employees have obtained first degree. This shows that more than 60% of the respondents have first degree. This may be due to the fact that the questionnaire was distributed purposively to respondents who can understand logistics and it's functioning in the company.

Respondents' Experience in the Organization

The respondents have been asked to indicate the number of years they have stayed in the organization. During data collection the respondents were asked only to write the number of years they spent in the organization. For analysis purpose the researcher categorize in to different groups as less than 2 years, 2-5 years, 6-10 years and Over 10 years. In accordance with table 4.2 7 respondents (5.5%) said that they stayed less than 2 years, 52 respondents (40.6%) said that they have been in the company for 2-5 years, 46 respondents (35.9%) replying that they have been in the company for 6-10 years and 22 respondents (17.2%) have been in the company for more than 10 years. The result from table 4.2 above showed that majority of (53.1%) the company's (KTSC) employees have been in the organization for 6 years and above. This

indicates that majority of respondents are appropriate to answer the research question and supposed to have information about kombolcha textile share company logistics practices and its performance level.

4.4 Descriptive Statistics

Based on the responses obtained from the participants, percentage, mean scores and standard deviations of each variable have been computed. Standard deviation shows how diverse responses are the participants give out on a particular constructs. In other words, the higher the standard deviation discloses the higher the disparity of the respondents view about a given dimension which means that respondents give variety of observation, and low standard deviation implies that respondents express close observation on a common matter. The statistical descriptive results of each of logistics practice constructs, logistics performance measures and organizational performance are presented as next from table 4.3-4.10. In each table under the percentage section column number 1, 2,3,4,5 represents strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and strongly agree respectively and the decimal numbers under each column of 1-5 indicate the portion of the respondents that show their agreement and disagreement on each item. Percentage, mean scores and standard deviation are computed for each item under each construct. The mean values are interpreted based on the assumption that Kidane (2012), mentioned the rule to the intervals for breaking the range in measuring variables that are captured with five point scale (that ranges from strongly disagree to strongly agree) is 0.8, which is actually found by dividing the difference between the maximum and minimum scores to the maximum score (5-1/5). Hence, a calculated individual and overall mean value that ranges from 1 to 1.80 implies strong disagreement, whereas the remaining ranges of 1.81 to 2.6, 2.61 to 3.4, 3.41 to 4.2 and 4.21 to 5.00 representing respondents' perceptions of disagreement, neutrality, agreement and strong agreement respectively (as cited by Melkamu, 2016).

4.4.1 Customer Service

In the modern business environment, which is characterized by the market globalization, rapid development and usage of new technologies, logistics activities have specific implications on business processes. Customer service management can create a basis for continuous sustained growth of operating incomes, and at the same time it provides its own positive corporate image in the market (Bowersox et al., 2002). Hence Customer service was considered as a measure of logistics practice and it was assessed by the items in the below table 4.3.

Table 4.3- Customer Service

	N	Percentage (%)					Mean	Std. Deviation
		1	2	3	4	5		
We have clearly defined customer service policy.	128	0.8	3.1	24.2	51.6	20.3	3.87500	.793676
We frequently monitor our Customers level of satisfaction	128		2.3	24.2	49.2	24.2	3.95313	.761881
We have customer friendly order capture and entry.	128			34.4	54.7	10.9	3.76562	.633505
We have various options for our customers to place and enter their orders. (e.g, telephone, mail, fax, internet).	128	3.1	2.3	7.0	42.2	45.3	4.2422	.92000
We have maintained real time inventory visibility to our customers.	128	2.3	7.8	18.0	47.7	24.2	3.8359	.96210
We have able to maintain flexible customer Order processing proactive to changes.	128		3.9	21.9	54.7	19.5	3.8984	.75127
We communicate quickly with customers if unusual changes occur.	128	2.3	3.9	10.2	65.6	18.0	3.9297	.80533
We have multiple collection and payment options. (e.g, mobile banking, electronic transfer, internet banking)	128	3.1	10.2	21.9	35.2	29.7	3.7813	1.07906
Overall mean							3.9102	.14970

Source: Field Survey, 2018

As indicated on the above table 4.3 about 51.6% of the respondents agreed and 20.3% strongly agreed, 24.2% neutral, 3.9% of the respondents almost disagreed on the item defined customer service policy with a mean and standard deviation of (M=3.87500, SD=0.793676). This indicated that over 70% of the respondents showed their agreement on customer service policy.

With regard to monitoring customers level of satisfaction 49.2% of the respondents agreed and 24.2% strongly agreed, 24.2% said neutral, 2.3% of respondents showed their disagreement with a mean and standard deviation of (M=3.95313, SD=0.761881). This indicates that more than

70% of the respondents are agreed that the company monitors its customer's level of satisfaction. Regarding customer friendly order capture and entry 54.7% of the respondents agreed and 10.9% strongly agreed 34.4% said they are neutral with mean and standard deviation of (M= 3.76562, SD= 0.633505). This depicts that over 60% of the respondents agreed that the company's order capture and entry is friendly for customers. It is also depicted on above table 4.3 about 42.2% of the respondents agreed and 45.3% strongly agreed, 7% neutral, almost 5.4% of the respondents disagreed concerning that the company has various options for customers to place and enter their orders with a mean and standard deviation value of (M=4.2422, SD=0.92000). This also indicates that over 80% of the respondents are agreed that the company has multiple options of order placement and entry. Concerned with inventory visibility for customers 47.7% of respondents agreed and 24.2% strongly agreed, 18% neutral, almost 10.1% of the respondents disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.8359, SD=0.96210). This depicts that more than 70% of the respondents agreed that the company maintained a real time inventory for customers. About 54.7% of respondents agreed and 19.5% strongly agreed, 21.9% neutral, 3.9% of respondents disagreed about flexible order processing with a mean and standard deviation score of (M=3.8984, SD=0.75127). More than 70% of the respondents agreed that the company has flexible order processing proactive to changes.

With regard to quick communication of unusual changes 65.6% of the respondents agreed and 18% strongly agreed, 10.6% said neutral, about 6.2% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.9297, SD=0.80533). This shows that over 80% of the respondents agreed that the company quickly communicates with customers if unusual changes occur. concerning multiple collection options 35.2% of the respondents agreed and 29.7% strongly agreed, 21.9% neutral, about 13.3% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.7813, SD=1.07906). This indicates that over 60% of the respondents agreed that the company has multiple collection options. Though majority of the respondents agreed that customer component of logistics is available in the company the portion of respondents that have been disagreed and neutral should not be underestimated since they may have the real information. The above table 4.3 also indicated that 87.5% of the mean are greater than 3.41 and 12.5% of the mean greater than 4.21 which shows that the respondents agree and strongly agree respectively that customer service is practiced in the company. The qualitative data collected through semi-structured interview reveals that, the company has been communicate and share information with

customers' particularly those wholesalers and distributors via telephone and e-mail communications are frequently used. The company order processing is also flexible but with maintaining inventory not using up to date information for order processing and forecasting of customers' needs, proper organizing of Invoicing and collection methods are also well known in the company's logistics though they are manual. During semi structured interview it is also found that the company does not measure and evaluate customer satisfaction level and it is found to be less practiced since the company has not been made a research regarding customers' level of satisfaction.

One of the informant said *"I have been in the company for more than 6 years and I did not remember that we have made an assessment concerning our customers' level of satisfaction. We have local and foreign customers, most of the time our local customers are factory/wholesalers. Only we believe that they are satisfied since our products are high quality and sold, orders come frequently from branches and customers; the problem is due to power irregularities and machine breakdowns we could not produce to maximum capacity and due to this stock outs occur at sometime"*. Despite the overall mean (M=3.9102) is also greater than 3.41 which showed that the respondents agreed that the company has well articulated customer service management; the qualitative data does not show that it is practiced to that extent. This takes us to the conclusion that customer service has less practiced in the company and it is in line with the study by Melkamu (2016) who found that logistics of customer service is practiced at a lesser extent in footwear manufacturing firms in Ethiopia. This poor practicing of customer service in the company would lead to losing customers and potential sales. In the literature it is identified that in competitive market of final products, the level of customer service can help firms get new and/or retain old customers (Melovic et al., 2015) and can grow in sales and market share. So that, the company should maintain close relationship with its customers and should provide customers superior quality products with in required delivery time at acceptable price so as to experience the best opportunities from logistics customer service. Another study by Mwangangi, (2016) also found that customers order process management is practiced among Kenyan manufacturing firms and customer service accounts 23.4% of the variation in firm performance.

4.4.2 Inventory Planning and Management

Inventory management is critical logistics function to an organization's success in today's competitive and dynamic market. This entails a reduction in the cost of holding stocks by

maintaining just enough inventories, in the right place and the right time and cost to make the right amount of needed products (Frazelle, 2002). Inventory management was also considered so as to measure logistics practice and it is illustrated in table 4.4 below.

Table 4.4- Inventory Management

	N	Percentage (%)					Mean	Std. Deviation
		1	2	3	4	5		
We have established inventory planning and control policy.	128		2.3	21.9	48.4	27.3	4.0078	.76843
With Improved forecast accuracy we have able to minimize lost sales and customer dissatisfactions.	128		1.6	11.7	59.4	27.3	4.1250	.66404
We have able to reduced lead times with efficient inventory planning. (e.g., economic order quantity).	128		4.7	21.1	57.0	17.2	3.8672	.74634
We frequently achieve lower purchase order/setup costs.	128	0.8	3.9	36.7	51.6	7.0	3.6016	.71364
We able to maintain minimum inventory with quick response and just in time.	128		8.6	22.7	53.9	14.8	3.7500	.81328
We frequently carious to make the various inventory carrying costs to the minimum.	128		1.6	31.3	53.1	14.1	3.7969	.69145
We able to maintain improved inventory visibility with our suppliers.	128	2.3	10.2	34.4	35.2	18.0	3.5625	.97811
We frequently deployed optimal inventory to customer's location timely.	128		0.8	13.3	53.1	32.8	4.1797	.68082
Overall mean							3.8613	.22856

Source: Field Survey, 2018

On the above table 4.4 it is indicated that 48.4% of the respondents agreed and 27.3% strongly agreed, 21.9% neutral about Inventory planning and control policy with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.0078, SD=0.76843). This indicates that more than 70% of the respondents agreed that the company has established Inventory planning and control policy. Regarding improved forecast accuracy 59.4% of the respondents agreed and 27.3% strongly agreed, 11.7%

said neutral, with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.1250, SD=0.66404). This shows that over 80% of the respondents agreed that the company has able to minimize lost sales and customer dissatisfaction with improved forecast accuracy. With regard to reduction of lead times 57% of the respondents agreed and 17.2% strongly agreed, 21.1% neutral, 4.7% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.8672, SD=.74634). This indicates over 70% of the respondents agreed that the company is able to reduce lead times with efficient inventory planning. About 51.6% of respondents agreed and 7% strongly agreed, 36.7% neutral, 3.9% disagreed concerned with achieving lower purchase order or set up costs with a mean and standard deviation value of (M=3.6016, SD=.71364). This indicates that over 58% of the respondents agreed that the company achieves lower purchase order or set up costs. With regard to maintaining minimum inventory 53.9% of the respondents agreed and 14.8% strongly agreed, 22.7% said neutral, 8.6% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.7500, SD=0.81328). This depicts that over 60% of the respondents agreed that the company has been able to maintain minimum inventory with quick response and just in time. About 53.1% of the respondents agreed and 14.1% strongly agreed, 31.3% neutral about minimize inventory carrying costs with a mean and standard deviation score of (M=3.7969, SD=0.69145). This indicates that over 60% of the respondents agreed that the company is carious to minimize various inventory carrying costs. Concerned with improved inventory visibility 35.2% of respondents agreed and 18% strongly agreed, 34.4% neutral, 10.2% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.5625, SD=0.97811). This shows that 53% of the respondents agreed that the company has improved inventory visibility and the rest said neutral and disagreed. Regarding optimal inventory deployment about 53.1% agreed and 32.8% strongly agreed, 13.3% neutral, with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.1797, SD=0.68082). This indicates that more than 80% of the respondents agreed that the company deploys an optimal inventory to customer's location.

The above Table 4.4 also indicated that the mean value of all the items is between 3.41 and 4.2 which show that the respondents agreed that inventory management is practiced in the company. In relation to the above results even though it shows inventory management is highly practice in the company the portion of respondents who disagreed and neutral should not be understated since they may have good understanding regarding the mentioned items and inventory management of the company. Additionally results from semi-structured interview indicate that communicating the available inventories with suppliers and customers through phones and

emails is a common practiced and the Company employs FIFO inventory control method and annually counts inventories when required for reports and financial statements. However; since the company is textile manufacturing lint cotton, packing plastics, several paints and chemicals are the main raw material inventories. the sourcing location is too far and the suppliers are not well equipped to have integration with; the company maintains too much inventory of each therefore advanced inventory management tools like just in time and quick response have not been applied in the company all the time the company's logistics is flexible through maintaining inventories of raw and finished products and the associated costs are high and its inventory planning and forecast is based on guesses from the previous years have not applied economic order quantity, MRP and ERP tools. For example lint cotton stays 15 up to 20 days only in the spinning production area so as to make it adapted to that environment before going to be processed.

During semi-structured interview it is also found that lead times is longer for the company's logistics system particularly for exported products. It is said that "*our customers are complaining not the quality of our products rather not conformance to their delivery requirements and not having electronic inventory visibility systems*". This leads us to conclude that the company is not practicing inventory management to the extent that could enhance overall performance. This suggests that it is costly for the company yet not having an advanced inventory planning systems available since a significant amount of a company's budget is invested on inventory. ineffective and inefficient management of inventory mean that the organization loses customers and sales will decline. For business firms on average around 40% of annual budget is allocated to inventory (Frazelle, 2002). This view is supported by Mwangangi (2016) found that inventory management alone explains firm performance by 20.7. This finding is similar with the finding by Melkamu (2016) inventory management is practiced at a lesser extent in Ethiopian footwear manufacturing firms.

4.4.3 Supply Management

A higher level of supply management interface capability automatically results in integration of logistics activities through seamless connection between suppliers and the manufacturer. It creates a strong positive influence on firm performance through the development of joint resources and the exchange of valuable information (Ondoro et al., 2013). Supply management

or procurement is also considered to measure logistics practices of the case company as illustrated on Table 4.5 below.

Table 4.5- Supply Management

	N	Percentage (%)					Mean	Std. Deviation
		1	2	3	4	5		
We have clearly established supplier service policy.	128	1.6	2.3	27.3	56.3	12.5	3.7578	.76071
We monitor and evaluate our suppliers' performance on a consistent basis.	128		0.8	18.8	57.8	22.7	4.0234	.66953
We have clearly defined criteria to select our suppliers.	128		0.8	16.4	57.8	25.0	4.0703	.66621
We have established criterion for supplier certification and reward.	128		0.8	21.1	57.0	21.1	3.9844	.67561
We maintained proactive exception reporting with suppliers.	128			34.4	48.4	17.2	3.8281	.69994
We frequently exchange information via electronic communication with suppliers (e.g. EDI, fax, and e-procurement).	128	1.6	6.3	28.9	39.1	24.2	3.7812	.93857
We able to reduce acquisition costs through purchase consolidation.	128	0.8	4.7	38.3	41.4	14.8	3.6484	.81897
We have practicing electronic fund transfer when payment to suppliers.	128	0.8	2.3	21.9	44.5	30.5	4.0156	.83227
We have maintained strong partnership and collaboration with suppliers.	128	0.8	2.3	6.3	55.5	35.2	4.2187	.73106
Overall mean							3.9253	.18143

Source: Field Survey, 2018

From table 4.5 above it is depicted that 56.3% of the respondents agreed and 12.5% strongly agreed, 27.3% neutral about supplier service policy with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.7578, SD=0.76071). This depicts that over 60% of the respondents agreed that the case company has established supplier service policy. Concerning supplier performance evaluation 57.8% of the respondents agreed and 22.7% strongly agreed, 18.8% neutral with mean and

standard deviation of (M=4.0234, SD=.66953). This signifies that more than 70% of the respondents agreed that the case company monitors its supplier's performance on consistent basis. It is also indicated that 57.8% of the respondents agreed and 25% strongly agreed, 16.4% neutral about criteria for supplier selection with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.0703, SD=0.66621). This signifies that over 80% of the respondents agreed that the case company has defined criteria to select suppliers. With regard to supplier certification and reward 57% of the respondents agreed and 21.1% strongly agreed, 21.1% neutral, with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.9844, SD=0.67561). This indicates that over 70% of the respondents agreed that the case company has defined criteria for supplier certification and reward.

Concerned with proactive exception reporting 48.4% of the respondents agreed and 17.2% strongly agreed 34.4% said neutral with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.8281, SD=.69994). This showed that over 60% of the respondents agreed that the case company has maintained exception reporting with suppliers. With regard to electronic information exchange 39.1% of the respondents agreed and 24.2% strongly agreed, 28.9% neutral, 6.3% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.7812, SD=.93857). This indicated that over 60% of respondents agreed that the case company is practicing electronic information exchange with suppliers. Concerning purchase consolidation 41.4% of the respondents agreed and 14.8% strongly agreed, 38.3% said neutral, 4.7% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.6484, SD=0.81897). This showed that 56% of the respondents agreed that the case company is able to reduce acquisition costs with purchase consolidation and the rest 44% said neutral and disagree. It is also depicted that 44.5% of the respondents agreed and 30.5% strongly agreed, 21.9% neutral about electronic fund transfer with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.0156, SD=.83227). This indicated that over 70% of the respondents agreed that the case company is practicing electronic fund transfer. About 55.5% of the respondents agreed and 35.2% strongly agreed, 6.3% neutral about supplier partnership and collaboration with mean and standard deviation (M=4.2187, SD=.73106). This signifies that over 80% of the respondents agreed that the case company has strong partnership and collaboration with suppliers. Table 4.5 above also indicated that 88.9% of the mean is between 3.41 and 4.2 indicating that respondents agree and 11.1% of the mean is more than 4.21 showing respondents strongly agree that supply management is practiced in the company. In addition to the above results obtained from the questionnaire results gathered from semi-structured interview show that the company's suppliers

are fixed for certain years one year or for two years in which the agreement is updated regularly based on the changes in the environment and has strong partnership and collaboration with those contracted suppliers. Contracting with suppliers enable the company's procurement units not to have periodical bid notification and moving to different location for sourcing. However; the Company does not have been made formal supplier performance evaluation and providing incentives hence the company makes agreements and contracts with suppliers that provide better prices, quality and delivery dates. The company is also share material needs and available inventory status information with its contracted suppliers. Most of the time the company orders and purchase in large quantities so as to reduce purchasing, transportation and related costs. The company also has not made any effort regarding certification and reward programs for suppliers. The grand mean of supply management in the above table is also (M= 3.9253) which indicate that procurement function is practiced in the company but the portion of respondents who disagreed should not be understated and the qualitative result does not show that all elements of supply management are incorporated to say it is implemented at best level. This would result to conclude that supply management/procurement is less practiced in the company.this has an implication for the company to re-examine its procurement practices since in todays competitivr market environment not having alliance with raw material suppliers would case the company volnurable to exatra costs for sourcing, poor quality of inputs and long procurement lead times. This is consistence with the finding by Melkamu (2016) studied on footwear manufacturing firms in Ethiopia and concluded that firms have no strong link with their suppliers. This result not in line with the finding by Ondoro et al. (2013) who investigate purchasing and supply management is practiced among Kenyan transport firms and supply management accounts for 39.8% of the variation in firm performance.

4.4.4 Transportation Management

Transport management is the planning, controlling and decision making on operational area of logistics that geographically moved and positioned inventory (Bowersox et al., 2002). Transportation management is also assessed so as to measure logistics practice of the company on table 4.6 below.

Table 4.6- Transportation Management

	N	Percentage (%)					Mean	Std. Deviation
		1	2	3	4	5		
We have efficient transportation services in moving materials	128	0.8	3.9	10.9	57.0	27.3	4.06250	.781176
We able to achieve in transit Shipments to the minimum.	128		10.2	15.6	53.9	20.3	3.8438	.86432
We have collaborative relationship with our transport Carriers.	128	3.9	3.1	7.8	55.5	29.7	4.0391	.92560
We have clear freight management principles.	128	3.1	1.6	13.3	62.5	19.5	3.9375	.82050
We have flexible Transportation service that can handle changes.	128	1.6	0.8	25.0	47.7	25.0	3.9375	.82050
We have achieved economies of scale via transport consolidation.	128		3.1	18.0	50.0	28.9	4.0469	.77215
We frequently Measure transport performance for delivery of our finished products.	128		4.7	8.6	54.7	32.0	4.1406	4.1406
We frequently Measure the transport performance of transport companies and rewarding them accordingly.	128	0.8	9.4	29.7	40.6	19.5	3.6875	.92003
Overall Mean							3.9619	.14426

Source: Field Survey, 2018

As shown on the table 4.6 above 57% of the respondents agreed and 27.3% strongly agreed, 10.9% neutral, 3.9% disagreed about efficient transportation service with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.06250, SD=.781176.). This is an indication that more than 80% of the respondents agreed that the company has an efficient transport service. Concerning transit shipment status 53.9% of the respondents agreed and 20.3% strongly agreed, 15.6% neutral, 10.2% disagreed, with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.8438, SD=.86432). This shows that over 70% of the respondents agreed about shipment practice of the company. With regard to collaborative relationship with carriers 55.5% of respondents agreed and 29.7% strongly agreed,

7.8% neutral, 7% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.0391, SD=.92560). This indicates that more than 80% of the respondents agreed that the company has collaborative relationship with transport carriers. About 62.5% of the respondents agreed and 19.5% strongly agreed, 13.3% neutral, 4.7% disagreed about freight management principles with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.9375, SD=.82050). This shows that over 80% of respondents agreed that the company has freight management principles. Concerned on flexible transportation service 47.7% of respondents agreed and 25% strongly agreed, 25% said neutral with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.9375, SD=.82050). This indicates that over 70% of the respondents agreed that the company has flexible transportation service. Regarding transport consolidation 50% of respondents agreed and 28.9% strongly agreed, 18% said neutral, 3.1% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.0469, SD=.77215). This also depicts that over 70% of the respondents agreed that the case company consolidates freights to achieve economies of scale. With regard to transport performance 54.7% of the respondents agreed and 32% strongly agreed, 8.6% neutral, 4.75 disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.1406, SD=.76059). This is an indication that over 80% of respondents agreed that the company measures its transport performance. About 40.6% of the respondents agreed and 19.5% strongly agreed, 29.7% neutral 9.4% disagreed about rewarding transport companies with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.6875, SD=.92003). This has an indication that around 60% of the respondents agreed that the case company reward transport companies based on their performance.

Table 4.6 above also indicated that the mean value of all the items is between 3.41 and 4.2 which show that the respondents agreed that transportation management is practiced in the company with the respective items. The qualitative data obtained through semi-structured interview shows that achieving economies of scale via transport consolidation practiced and understood very well in the company. However; the company's transportation service is not efficient, fail to minimize transit shipment, unable truck on way freights due to the fact that the company does not applied advanced transport management tools like, fleet control systems, route planning and vehicle inspection schedule, tracking system, vehicle scheduling so as to provide flexible transportation service, enhance collaboration with carriers and to make visible vehicles, in transit shipments are where available. One of the interviewee stated that "*Concerning transportation service of our company there are only limited trucks owned by the organization. Lint cotton and exported products are transported through the company's own vehicles. Vehicles owned by the company*

are not enough to provide the company's transportation requirement and the company frequently uses rental vehicles due to this there are delays and frequent vehicle fee increments. Hence it is difficult to say that the transportation service of the company is efficient since there are frequent irregularities and obstacle". The overall mean (M=3.9619) indicate that it is greater than 3.41 and respondents agreed transportation management well managed in the company but the qualitative result does not support that it does and this qualitatively obtained data is more trustful than the questionnaire. Therefore; this leads to the conclusion that the company is not using transportation management strategically to make it helpful in achieving the company's objective. Transportation is a logistics function that makes available inputs to production and products to customers. Not having flexible and efficient transportation assisted with advanced thecnologies will led the company to poor customer service, high cost due to delays and inventories and finally cases inefficient logistics system because of more than half of logistics cost is incurred for transportation. The result of this study similar with the finding by Melkamu (2016) the strategic use of transport management in Ethiopian footwear manufacturing firms is very low. The study by Mukolweand Wanyoike (2015) indicated that Strategic use of logistics activitiessuch as transport and distribution allows faster and cost effective flow of goods and raw materials and has adept in Kenyan sugar manufacturing.

4.4.5 Warehouse Management

Warehousing is an important part of a firm's logistics system that stores products (raw materials, parts, goods-in-process and finished goods) at and between points of origin and points of consumption (Murphy et al., 2008). Warehouse management was also included as a measure of logistics practices in the case company and the result is illustrated in the below table 4.7.

Table 4.7- Warehouse Management

	N	Percentage (%)					Mean	Std. Deviation
		1	2	3	4	5		
We able to design a warehouse convenient for loading and unloading.	128	1.6	1.6	14.8	47.7	34.4	4.11719	.828822
We have standard guidelines to receive and store materials.	128		3.1	13.3	41.4	42.2	4.22656	.795804
We always properly store materials and	128		3.1	9.4	59.4	28.1	4.12500	.698705

timely disbursing to user functions.								
We receive materials with assurance of quantity and quality as per ordered.	128		2.3	7.8	50.8	39.1	4.26562	.704143
We have able to minimize damages of product in the warehouse.	128		1.6	14.1	48.4	35.9	4.18750	.729038
We have maintained up to date records and reports of warehouse data.	128	1.6	7.8	17.2	46.9	26.6	3.89063	.941053
We have adequate shelves in warehouse to facilitate order picking.	128		4.7	22.7	32.8	39.8	4.07813	.901524
We able to packaged and boxed products for more convenient for use.	128		0.8	7.8	55.5	35.9	4.26563	.633505
We have skilled personnel that can handle warehouse activities.	128	0.8	1.6	11.7	36.7	49.2	4.32031	.802885
Overall Mean							4.1641	.13008

Source: Field Survey, 2018

From the table 4.7 above 47.7% of the respondents agreed, and 34.4% strongly agreed strongly disagreed, 14.8% neutral about convenient warehouse design with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.11719, SD=0.828822). This indicates over 70% of respondents agreed that the company has a convenient warehouse. About 41.4% of the respondents agreed and 42.2% strongly agreed, 13.3% neutral about standard guideline with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.22656, SD=.795804). This implies that over 80% of the respondents agreed that the case company has standard warehouse guideline. With Regarding to properly store materials and timely disburse to user functions 59.4% of respondents agreed and 28.1% strongly agreed, 9.4% neutral with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.12500, SD=.698705). This shows that over 80% of respondents agreed that the case company properly store and disburse materials. Concerned on receive materials with assurance of quality and quantity 50.8% of the respondents agreed and 39.1% strongly agreed, 7.8% neutral with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.26562, SD=.704143) implying that over 80% of respondents agreed that the company receive materials with assurance of quality and quantity. About 48.45% of the respondents agreed and 35.9% strongly agreed, 14.1% neutral about product damage minimization in the warehouse with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.18750, SD=.729038) implying that more than 80% of the respondents agreed

that the company able to minimize damages of product in the warehouse. With regard to up-to-date record and reports of warehouse data 46.9% of the respondents agreed and 26.6% strongly agreed , 17.2% neutral, 7.8% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.89063, SD=.941053) indicating that over 60% of the respondents agreed that the case company has up-to-date record and reports of warehouse data. Concerned on adequate shelves to facilitate order picking 32.8% of respondents agreed and 39.8% strongly agreed, 22.7% neutral, 4.7% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.07813, SD=.901524) implying that over 70% of respondent agreed that the company has maintained adequate shelves. With regard to convenient package of products 55.5% of the respondents agreed and 35.9% strongly agreed, 7.8% neutral with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.26563, SD=.633505) indicating that over 80% of respondents agreed that the company's product is packaged convenient for use. About 36.7% of the respondents agreed and 49.2% strongly agree, 11.7% neutral about skilled personnel with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.32031, SD=.802885) indicating that more than 80% of respondents agreed that the company has skilled personnel to handle warehouse activities. Table 4.7 above also indicated that 55.6% of the mean are between 3.41 and 4.20 where as 44.4% of the mean are greater than 4.21 implying that the respondents agree and strongly agree respectively that warehouse management is practiced in the company. The qualitative data obtained from semi-structured interview also indicated the company has warehouses convenient to store raw and finished products, standard guideline for storage of materials, proper storage products in the warehouse, assurance of quality and quantity inflow and outflow materials and products, proper package of products warehouse activities are practice in the company. The overall mean value (M=4.1641) also indicate that the respondents agreed that warehouse management activities understood in the company.

Unfortunately; the company does not have been applied warehouse management system software's, radio frequency identification tool and advanced ICT tools to facilitate and maintain up to date record and reports of warehouse data. Loading and unloading is manual, there is no lift trucks in the company. One of the interviewee said that, *“There are two main warehouse in the company; the one is used for lint cotton and related inputs when arrive and until used. The other is used for the storage of finished goods until they are delivered to sales centers and sold to customers or distributed to sales centers or different selling branches and to other retailers. There are also certain storage areas in each processing unit so as to put temporarily the output*

of that process until brought to the next production process”. This shows warehouse management is at least there in the company though its operation is not supported with advanced warehouse operation tools. A similar study finding by Mukolwe and Wanyoike (2015) suggested that warehousing activities greatly enhances accuracy, speed of operations and reduces wastage, improves order process and customer service in Kenyan sugar manufacturing firms and is managed very well.

4.4.6 Logistics Information System

Adewoye (2010) stated that companies are now equipped to make effective use of data, from warehouse management systems, which contain information on supplier/customer warehouse inventory levels and key customer ordering patterns and transportation management systems with integrated logistics information system which facilitates information pertaining to the location of important supply chain assets, such as products or vehicles is typically stored. Logistics information system was the other dimension considered to measure logistics practice as illustrated below table 4.8.

Table 4.8- Logistics Information System

	N	Percentage (%)					Mean	Std. Deviation
		1	2	3	4	5		
We have faster and Smooth information flow to all logistics functions.	128		5.5	5.5	68.9	20.3	4.0391	.69194
We able to provide web-based information system for all clients.	128	0.8	10.9	18.8	56.3	13.3	3.7031	.86361
We have provided basic communication tools such as email, telephone, fax, etc for logistics activities.	128	1.6	1.6	14.8	44.5	37.5	4.1484	.84266
We have used product identification and tracking system (such as bar code, EDI, IT solution or RFID) to support logistics activities.	128	7.8	8.6	48.4	25.0	10.2	3.2109	1.00903
We maintain easier collection/payable management with logistics information	128		2.3	33.6	47.7	16.4	3.7812	.74175

system.								
We frequently are looking for new or technologically-advanced equipments for logistics operations.	128	3.1	10.9	39.8	38.3	7.8	3.3672	.89505
We have achieved optimal inventory with accurate information.	128		4.7	15.6	69.5	10.2	3.8516	.65316
We able to minimize operational costs with logistics information system.	128		5.5	9.4	68.0	17.2	3.9688	.69800
We have able to achieve smooth flow of materials and products.	128			11.7	60.9	27.3	4.1563	.60753
We have Used electronic customer feedback	128		10.9	39.8	35.2	14.1	3.5234	.86911
Overall Mean							3.7750	.32507

Source: Field Survey, 2018

As depicted table 4.8 above 68.9% of the respondents agreed, 20.3% strongly agreed 5.5% neutral, and 5.5% disagreed, about faster and smooth information flow with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.0391, SD=.69194) implying that over 80% of the respondents agreed that the company has faster and smooth information flow for logistics functions. With regard to web based information system 56.3% of the respondents agreed and 13.3% strongly agreed, 18.8% neutral, 10.9% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.7031, SD=.86361) showing that over 60% of the respondents agreed that the company provides web base information to its clients.

Concerning basic communication tools 44.5% of respondents agreed and 37.5% strongly agreed, 14.8% neutral with mean and standard deviation of (M=4.1484, SD=.84266) implying that over 70% of the respondents agreed that the company provides basic communication tools. About 25% of the respondents agreed and 10.2% strongly agreed, 48.4% neutral, 16.4% disagreed about the use of product identification and tracking system with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.2109, SD=1.00903) implying that most respondents are neutral and disagreed about the practice of product identification and tracking system. Regarding easier collection and payable management 47.7% of the respondents agreed and 16.4% strongly agreed, 33.6% neutral with mean and standard deviation of (M=3.7812, SD=.74175) implying that around 60% of the

respondents agreed that the company has easier collection and payable management with logistics information system. About 38.3% of the respondents agreed and 7.8% strongly agreed, 39.9% neutral, almost 14% disagreed concerned on the application of new or technologically advanced equipment with mean and standard deviation of ($M=3.3672$, $SD=.89505$) indicating that around 39% of respondents are neutral about that the company in applying technologically advanced equipment to facilitate logistics activities. With regard to optimal inventory 69.5% of respondents agreed and 10.2% strongly agreed, 15.6% neutral, 4.7% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of ($M=3.8516$, $SD=.65316$) indicating that over 70% of respondents agreed that the company is maintaining optimal inventory with accurate logistics information.

About 68% of the respondents agreed and 17.2% strongly agreed, 9.4% neutral, 5.5% disagreed about minimize operational costs with logistics information system with mean and standard deviation of ($M=3.9688$, $SD=.69800$) implying that over 80% of respondents agreed that the company able to minimize operational costs with logistics information system. With regard to smooth flow of materials and products 60.9% of the respondents agreed and 27.3% strongly agreed, 11.7% said neutral with mean and standard deviation ($M=4.1563$, $SD=.60753$) showing that over 80% of the respondents agree that there is smooth flow of materials and products in the company. Concerned with electronic customer feedback 35.2% of respondents agreed and 14.1% strongly agreed, 39.8% said neutral, 10.9% disagreed with mean and standard deviation of ($M=3.5234$, $SD=.86911$) which implies around 40% of the respondents are neutral about the provision of electronic customer feedback in the company. It also depicted on Table 4.9 above that the mean value of all the items is between 3.41 and 4.2 which show that the respondents agreed that logistics information system is available in the company. The overall mean value ($M=3.7750$) is also above 3.41 showing that respondents agreed that the company has logistics information system.

The qualitative data gathered via semi-structured interview affirms that Smooth and faster information flow, basic communication tools such email, telephone, fax, smooth flow of materials and products have been very known and practiced in the company. However; logistics information system components web based information system, application of advanced equipments for logistics activities, product identification and tracking systems such as bar code, EDI, IT solution or RFID are not applied by the company that can facilitate logistics activities so as to have improved logistics functions. The interviewee said that, *“Even though it does not say*

logistics information system the company have department that is called management information system on which any information connected with the company is maintained. For example a transaction with suppliers and customers, letters communicated with the company, sales and purchase reports, plan and performance reports of the company's departments, information connected with inventories, transportation costs and related reports maintained in this department". This qualitative result suggests that though it is not supported with updated technologies the company at least maintains separate information management functions that can facilitate logistics process and overall operations of the company. A research finding by Mukolwe and Wanyoike (2015) indicated that logistics information system is well understood by executives in sugar manufacturing firms in Kenya and suggested that effective management of information flow improves the company's internal and external processes.

Logistics activities are imperative for both manufacturing and service organizations. Logistics ensures the availability of the right products in the right quantity to the designated customers at the required time span. Managing logistics activities influences firm performance in terms of increment on sales and profitability (Harrison and van Hoek, 2008). Basically, the reason for existence of business firm is to provide customer needs. Logistics is a company's function committed to execute all process from raw material supply, inventory control, proper warehouse operations, and distribution to ultimately serve the designated customer needs. This implies that fail to do well at logistics activities mean that losing a business since logistics actually involved in the management of procurement, inventories, transportation and customer response. In general the interviewed participants also said that *"in our company we do not have a single logistics department but the basic logistics functions are performed by procurement and property control department and others are scattered to marketing and distributions areas"*. This shows that logistics activities are not carried out in the company by a single designated department. This denotes that the company's logistics process follows the traditional configuration that logistics activities spread throughout various organizational functions. The roles that logistics provides, the opportunities that excellent logistics brings like, significant cost saving and enhanced customer service could not be accessed unless maintaining well coordinated logistics process assisted with advanced logistics information technologies that optimizes common objective. Most of the time logistics activities are conflict each other if not facilitated and optimized by a dedicated department. Hence, with having logistics activities spread to

various functions which maximize its own objectives; the company should not expect positive results from such inefficient logistics system.

4.4.7 Logistics Performance measures

Chow et al. (1994) have defined logistics performance as the extent to which goals such as sales growth, job security and working conditions, customer satisfaction, product availability, cost-efficiency, profitability, social responsibility, on-time delivery, keeping promises, low loss and damage, fair prices for inputs, and flexibility are achieved. It is recognized that there are a number of significant connections between logistics performance and shareholder value. Consistent logistics performance measures ensure that cost-efficient, damage-free logistics objectives can be get achieved. Enhanced logistics performance achieved through immediate improvements can often increase revenue or decrease cost sufficiently (Bowersox, et al., 2002). The following table 4.9 portrays the distribution of logistics performance measures i.e., cost, quality, time to deliver and flexibility.

Table 4.9- Perception of Respondents on Logistics Performance Measures

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Logistics Cost			
We able to meet customer requirements at low cost.	128	3.7578	.68443
We able to achieve efficient capacity utilization.	128	3.9141	.67611
We able to minimize cost with safety stocks.	128	4.0234	.74733
We able to minimize cost with continuous improvement philosophy.	128	3.9922	.84645
We run operation with less Production cost.	128	3.9297	.86200
We maintains low manpower costs as compared to main competitors	128	3.8750	1.02719
We achieve low distribution costs as compared to main competitors	128	3.6406	.79104
We able to provide competitive prices.	128	4.0313	.75229
Overall Mean		3.8955	.13629
Logistics service quality			
We offer high quality products to our customer.	128	4.2109	.83856
We billed invoices accurately.	128	4.0625	.81085

We deliver product orders without damage.	128	4.3984	.70252
We maintain stock out level to the minimum.	128	4.0156	.80338
We fulfilled orders accurately.	128	4.2344	.69287
We deliver orders with greater shipping accuracy.	128	4.0703	.65428
We achieve high Percentage of orders without quality problems.	128	4.3281	.56275
We Employ continual improvement programs for sustainable quality.	128	4.4219	.62253
Overall Mean		4.2178	.15744
Time to deliver			
We deliver customer order on time.	128	4.0156	.63969
We frequently minimize delivery lead time.	128	3.9297	.70077
We frequently able to minimize purchase Order cycle-time.	128	3.8672	.87278
We Offer greater percentage of accurate timely delivery.	128	4.1641	.68479
We enter customer orders timely.	128	4.0234	.78835
We solve customer complaints in short time.	128	4.0547	.66769
We achieve short order processing time.	128	4.1641	.70741
Overall Mean		4.0313	.11059
Logistics Flexibility			
We have responsive logistic system to special orders.	128	3.8281	.69994
We have responsive logistic system to the instability of environment.	128	4.0078	.79858
We are flexible to acceptable number of changes by orders.	128	4.0547	.82585
We Accommodate delivery time for specific needs of customers.	128	4.1953	.71053
We have Quicker responses to changes with suppliers.	128	3.7969	.80705
We able to cope with the range of customer demand.	128	3.8984	.66213
We offer frequent deliveries for customers.	128	3.9219	.83816
We able to meet precise needs of customers in less time.	128	4.1016	.85886
Overall Mean		3.9756	.13834

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The Table 4.9 above shows that the mean value of all the items of logistics cost is between 3.41 and 4.20 which show that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics is carrying out logistics activities at low cost. In the table 4.9 above the mean and standard deviation of meeting customer requirements at low cost is (M=3.7578, SD=.68443) indicating that the respondents agreed that the company is meeting customer requirements at low cost. The mean and standard deviation value (M=3.9141, SD=.67611) about efficient capacity utilization also indicates that the respondents agreed that the company is efficient at logistics capacity utilization. With regard to minimizing costs with safety stocks the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0234, SD=.74733) implying that the respondents agreed that the company is able to minimize the costs associated with safety stocks. The mean and standard deviation value (M=3.9922, SD=.84645) about minimizing cost with continuous improvement philosophy indicates that the respondents agreed that the case company is able to minimize cost with continuous improvement philosophy for quality enhancement. The mean and standard deviation value (M=3.9297, SD=.86200) about running operation with less Production cost also implies that the respondents agreed that the company is running logistics operations at low cost. With regard to maintaining low manpower costs the mean and standard deviation value (M=3.8750, SD=1.02719) indicating that the respondents agreed that the company is able to maintain low logistics manpower costs. Regarding achieving low distribution costs the mean and standard deviation value (M=3.6406, SD=.79104) indicate that the respondents agreed that the company is able to achieve low distribution costs of logistics. Concerned with provide competitive prices the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0313, SD=.75229) shows that the respondents agreed that the company is able to provide competitive price.

The above Table 4.9 also depicts that 37.5% of the mean are greater than 3.41 and less than 4.2 indicating respondents agreed on that item and 62.5% of the mean are greater than 4.21 showing that respondents strongly agreed on that the company's logistics function is capable of providing high logistics service quality and providing high performance products free from damage and defects. Specifically each items are described as follow; regarding on offering high quality products to customer the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.2109, SD=.83856) indicates that the respondents agreed that company is offering high quality products. About billed invoices accurately the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0625, SD=.81085) which indicates that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics function is billed invoices accurately.

Concerned on deliver product orders without damage the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0625, SD=.81085) shows that the respondents agreed that the company provides damage free products. Concerned on maintain stock out level to the minimum the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0156, SD=.80338) indicates that the respondents agreed that company able to maintain stock out level to the minimum. With regard to fulfilled orders accurately the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.2344, SD=.69287) indicating that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics fulfils orders accurately. Concerned on deliver orders with greater shipping accuracy the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0703, SD=.65428). This implies that over 80% of the respondents agreed that the company's logistics deliver orders with greater shipping accuracy. About deliver orders without quality problems the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.3281, SD=.56275) indicating that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics is delivering orders without quality problems. With regard to continual improvement programs for sustainable quality the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.4219, SD=.62253) which implies that the respondent agreed that the company employs continual improvement programs for sustainable quality.

As it is also indicated on Table 4.9 above that the mean value of all the items of time to deliver logistics performance measure is between 3.41 and 4.2 which shows that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics function is capable of timely delivers customers requirements. The specific value of the items can be explained about deliver customer order on time the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0156, SD=.63969) shows that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics system delivers orders on time. With regard to minimizing delivery lead time the mean and standard deviation value (M=3.9297, SD=.70077) implying that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics able to minimize delivery lead times. Concerning on minimizing purchase Order cycle-time the mean and standard deviation value (M=3.8672, SD=.87278) implying that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics system is able to minimize purchase Order cycle-time. In relation to offering greater percentage of accurate timely delivery the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.1641, SD=.68479) implying that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics function offer greater percentage of accurate timely delivery. With reference to enter customer orders timely the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0234, SD=.78835) implying that the company able to enter customer orders timely. As regards solving customer complaints in short time the mean and

standard deviation value (M=4.0547, SD=.66769) indicating that the respondents agreed that the company able to solve customer complaints in short time. Concerning achieve short order processing time the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.1641, SD=.70741) showing that the respondents agreed that the company achieves short order processing time. Additionally As indicated on Table 4.9 above that the mean value of all the items of flexibility logistics performance measure is between 3.41 and 4.2 which show that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics function is responsive enough for various changes. With reference to responsive logistic system value mean and standard deviation of (M=3.8281, SD=.69994) and (M=4.0078, SD=.79858) implying that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics function is responsive to special orders and environmental changes. Concerned on flexible to changes of orders the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0547, SD=.82585). This indicates that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics is flexible to changes in orders.

As regards accommodating delivery time the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.1953, SD=.71053) implying that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics able to accommodate delivery time needs of customer. With regard to providing quicker responses to changes with suppliers the mean and standard deviation value (M=3.7969, SD=.80705) implying that the respondents agreed that the company provide quicker responses to changes with suppliers. Concerned on cope up with a range of customer demand the mean and standard deviation value (M=3.8984, SD=.66213) which indicates that the respondents agreed that the company is capable of cope up with a range of customer demand changes. Regarding offer frequent deliveries for customers the mean and standard deviation value (M=3.9219, SD=.83816) implying that the respondents agreed that the company able to offer frequent deliveries. With regard to meeting precise needs of customers in less time the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.1016, SD=.85886) indicating that the respondents agreed that the company able to meet precise needs of customers in less time.

The qualitative data obtained through semi-structured interview confirmed that the company's logistics performance is measured based on indicators related with logistics cost, responsiveness and logistics flexibility. One interviewee stated that *"mostly our logistics costs are high due to we maintain raw material inventories for long period and there are stock outs because of machine breakdowns and capacity inefficiencies. On the other way our foreign customers complain for not timely delivering to the port that is due to custom procedure problems"*. It has

also said that “Departments are evaluated based on how well achieved its functional goals and objective in the company. Logistics activites of our company is also measured based on the usage and outlay of finance budgeted to the department, and how well it achieved the logistics activities of the company and based on the effort that the departments makes control and maintain damage free and waste free materials, products, providing products to customers without quality problems. Additionally it is evaluated based on the responsiveness and flexibility of the logistics service and the controlling performance”. Logistics function and good performance in logistics has also great role on the company’s performance. The informants also said that “The well functioning of logistics function has a big role to the health of the company as whole. Therefore, especially in our company around 60% of the company’s annual budget is allocated to for procurement, marketing and sales, transportation, production and related areas the health of logistics performance has a great contribution for the company as whole to achieve financial and market related the company’s objectives

4.4.8 Organizational Performance

Even though firm performance is viewed in a variety of ways by various authors Schramm and Morschett, (2006), regards that marketing performance (sales and market share growth) and financial performance (return on investment and profit growth) are consequences of performance of logistics activities. The below table 4.10 illustrates mean and standard deviation of items of which considered to measure organizational performance.

Table 4.10- Perception of Respondents on Organizational Performance

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Market share.	128	4.0859	.69901
The growth of market share.	128	4.1484	.71088
The growth of sales.	128	4.2344	.68141
Return on investment.	128	3.7656	.79847
Growth in return on investment.	128	3.7969	.85444
Profit margin on sales.	128	4.2734	.71777
Overall competitive position.	128	4.0391	.86400
Overall Mean		4.0491	.19997

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Table 4.10 above also indicated that 71.4% of the mean is between 3.41 and 4.2 indicating that respondents agree that there is an increase on that items and 28.6% of the mean is more than 4.21 showing respondents agree that there is significant increase on the items that are considered to measure organizational performance. The description of the specific items is; with regard to market share of the company the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0859, SD=.69901) implies that the respondents agreed that there is an increment in the company's market share for the last five years. With regard to growth of market share of the company the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.1484, SD=.71088) indicating that there is a significant growth in market share of the company in the last five years. About growth of sales of the company the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.2344, SD=.68141) which implies that the respondents agreed that there is an increase in growth of sales of the case company in the last five years. With regard to return on investment the mean and standard deviation value (M=3.7656, SD=.79847) indicating that the respondents agreed that there is an increase in return on investment of the company in the last five years. In relation to growth in return on investment the mean and standard deviation value (M=3.7969, SD=.85444) implying that the respondents agreed that there is an increase in the growth in return on investment of the company in the last five years. Regarding Profit margin on sales the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.2734, SD=.71777) which shows that the respondents agreed that there is an increase in Profit margin on sales of the company in the last five years. Regarding overall competitive position of the company the mean and standard deviation value (M=4.0391, SD=.86400) indicating that the respondents agreed that there is an increase in overall competitive position of the company in the last five years.

The qualitative data gathered via semi-structured interview as revealed by one of the interviewee *“In our company annually different functions evaluate and measure their performance based on their individual objectives and responsibilities and their activity performance is submitted and combined to evaluate the company's overall financial, sales and marketing objectives. For example our company frequently uses performance indicators like, profitability ratio, liquidity ratio, activity (efficiency) ratio, financial leverage ratio, ratio of cost and expense to net sales. After recent years particularly after 2002/03 E.C with the support of government funds and by importing setting up modern and advanced textile machines the company has show many improvements in the quality of products and market share and acceptance. However; still until two years and three years before the company's income statement shows negative net income”*.

The secondary data obtained from the company’s annual report for instance shows that in the end of 2012 the company’s net income was (10,618,677.65) and at the end of 2013 it was (2,240,853.15). The return on investment of the company in 2012 was 0.0817 and it was 0.0178 in 2013, the total asset turnover ratio in 2012 was 1.4516 and it was 1.8728 in 2013. The total sales of the company in 2012 were 188,581,527.35 birr and it was 235, 266,266.85 birr in 2013 showing a growth by 19.8%. This indicates that the company is experiencing a significant improvement in sales though it has failed in cost saving and reduction of the various expenses that makes the company to have negative net income.

4.5 Inferential Statistics

4.5.1 Correlation Analysis

In this section the researcher tried to accomplish the objective of the study through applying Pearson correlation analysis as it is the most widely used methods of measuring the strength and direction of relationship between and among variables. Correlations are the measure of the linear relationship between two or more variables. A correlation coefficient has a value ranging from -1 to 1. Values that are closer to the absolute value of 1 indicate that there is a strong relationship between the variables being correlated whereas values closer to 0 indicates that there is little or no linear relationship. As described by Pallant (2007), the correlation is a commonly used measure of the size of an effect: values of ± 0.1 represent a small effect, ± 0.3 is a medium effect and ± 0.5 is a large effect. In this section, correlation analysis conducted in the light of each research objectives developed. The relationship between logistics practice and logistics performance; logistics practice and organizational performance; logistics performance measures and organizational performance were investigated using correlation analysis. This provided correlation Coefficients which indicated the strength and direction of relationship. The significance value also indicated the probability of this relationships significance.

4.5.1.1 Correlation between logistics practice dimensions and logistics performance

Table 4.11-correlation between logistics practice dimensions and logistics performance

		CS	IM	SM	TM	WM	LIS	LP
CS	Pearson Correlation	1	.511**	.530**	.534**	.567**	.525**	.643**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128

IM	Pearson Correlation	.511**	1	.399**	.430**	.547**	.461**	.485**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	1	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
SM	Pearson Correlation	.530**	.399**	1	.481**	.480**	.554**	.579**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
TM	Pearson Correlation	.534**	.430**	.481**	1	.569**	.403**	.478**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
WM	Pearson Correlation	.567**	.547**	.480**	.569**	1	.605**	.595**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
LIS	Pearson Correlation	.525**	.461**	.554**	.403**	.605**	1	.737**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
LP	Pearson Correlation	.643**	.485**	.579**	.478**	.595**	.737**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The logistics dimensions (customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management, warehouse management and logistics information system) their relation with logistics performance was computed in the above table 4.11. The result of correlation matrix between each logistics dimensions and logistics performance is analyzed as follow: As it is indicated in the table 4.11 above, there is strong positive correlation between customer service (CS) and logistics performance (LP) with a correlation coefficient of 0.643 ($r=0.643$) and significance is 0.000. Therefore, customer service and logistics performance are strongly correlated. Table 4.11 also depict that as there is moderate and positive relationship between inventory management (IM) and logistics performance (LP) with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.485 ($r=0.485$) and significance value is 0.000. This significance tells that there is

medium relationship between the two. Additionally Pearson correlation test indicated in the table 4.11 also described that there is significant positive correlation between supply management (SM) and logistics performance. In other words supply management has large effect on logistics performance with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.579 ($r=0.579$) with significance level of 0.000. There is also medium association between transportation management (TM) and logistics performance (LP) with Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.478 ($r=0.478$) and significance value of 0.000 as indicated the table above. There is strong positive correlation between warehouse management (WM) and logistics performance (LP) with a correlation coefficient of 0.595 ($r=0.595$) and significance is value 0.000. Another correlation is made between logistics information system (LIS) and logistics performance (LP) and they are strongly correlated with correlation coefficient 0.737 ($r=0.737$) and significance is value 0.000. Therefore, logistics information system and logistics performance (LP) are strongly correlated. All the independent variables (CS, IM, SM, TM, WM, and LIS) are positively correlated with the dependent variable (logistics performance) at a significance value of 0.01. The finding is consistent with the work of (Mwangangi, 2016) that also showed that logistics activities such as (customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management, warehouse management and logistics information system) have strong positive association with the improved performance of logistics in the case of manufacturing firms in Kenyan.

4.5.1.2 Correlation between combined logistics dimensions and logistics performance

Table 4.12-correlation between combined logistics dimensions and logistics performance

		logistics practice	logistics performance
logistics practice	Pearson Correlation	1	.724**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	128	128
logistics performance	Pearson Correlation	.724**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	128	128

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS, 2018

As indicated on the above table 4.12, the Pearson correlation test was conducted between logistics practices (combined logistics dimensions) and logistics Performance (LP), the results shows that there is significantly strong correlation between logistics practice dimensions and logistics Performance. In other words logistics practices and logistics Performance has positive relationship with correlation coefficient of 0.724 ($r=0.724$) which is a large effect and significant at 0.01. Also Odhiambo et al., (2017) mentioned on their finding that there is a positive causal relationship between logistics practice and logistics performance.

4.5.1.3 Correlation between Logistics practice dimensions and organizational performance

Table 4.13-correlation between logistics practice dimensions and organizational performance

		CS	IM	SM	TM	WM	LIS	OP
CS	Pearson Correlation	1	.511**	.530**	.534**	.567**	.525**	.324**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
IM	Pearson Correlation	.511**	1	.399**	.430**	.547**	.461**	.224*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.011
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
SM	Pearson Correlation	.530**	.399**	1	.481**	.480**	.554**	.279**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.001
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
TM	Pearson Correlation	.534**	.430**	.481**	1	.569**	.403**	.347**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
WM	Pearson Correlation	.567**	.547**	.480**	.480**	1	.605**	.378**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
LIS	Pearson Correlation	.525**	.461**	.554**	.403**	.605**	1	.511**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
OP	Pearson Correlation	.324**	.224*	.279**	.347**	.378**	.511**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.011	.001	.000	.000	.000	

N	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).							
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).							

Source: Field Survey, 2018

Based on the above table 4.13, the result of correlation matrix between each logistics practice constructs and Organizational performance (OP) is analyzed as follow: As per the table 4.13 above showed, customer service (CS) positively related to organizational performance (OP) with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.324 ($r=0.324$) and significance value 0.000. This significance tells that there is medium effect and positive relationship between customer service and organizational performance (OP). Table 4.13 also depict that as there is small effect and positive association between inventory management (IM) and organizational performance (OP) with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.224 ($r=0.224$) significance value 0.00. This significance tells that there is small effect and positive relationship between inventory management and organizational performance. On the other hand the Pearson correlation test indicated in the table 4.13, also showed that there is small effect and positive correlation between supply management (SM) and organizational performance (OP) with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.279 ($r=0.279$) and significance value is 0.001. This significance tells that there is significant association of supply management and organizational performance. As per the above table 4.13, the correlation test conducted between transportation management (TM) and organizational performance, clearly indicates that there is moderate and positive relation between the two. The result of correlation coefficient showed 0.347 ($r=0.347$) and significance value is 0.000 which indicates as there is significant relation between them. The correlation test on warehouse management (WM) and Organizational Performance (OP) also shown a medium effect and positive correlation with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.378 ($r=0.378$) and significance value 0.000. This significance tells that there is significant relation between warehouse management (WM) and Organizational Performance (OP). Table 4.13 above, also depicts that as there is a large effect and positive relationship between logistics information system (LIS) and organizational performance (OP) with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.511 ($r=0.511$) significance value is 0.000. As table 4.13 above, indicated all the independent variables are positively correlate with the dependent variable 0.01 and 0.05 level of significant.

In connection to this fact (Odhiambo et al., 2017) also proved that logistics activities has significant relation to improvement of the organizational performance.

4.5.1.4 Correlation between combined logistics practice dimensions and organizational performance

Table 4.14-correlation between combined logistics dimensions and organizational performance

		logistics practice	organizational performance
logistics practice	Pearson Correlation	1	.417**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	128	128
organizational performance	Pearson Correlation	.417**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	128	128

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2018

Based on Pearson correlation test between logistics practices (combined logistics dimensions) and Organizational Performance conducted on the above table 4.14, the results shows that there is significantly medium correlation between logistics practices dimensions and organizational Performance with correlation coefficient of 0.417 ($r=0.417$) and significance value 0.000. The research results, obtained from the study by Gunasekaran and Ngai, (2003) indicated that, logistics practices have significant positive Relationship with the improvement of company performance.

4.5.1.5 Correlation between Logistics performance measures and organizational performance

Table 4.15-correlation between logistics performance measures and organizational performance

		Cost	quality	Time to deliver	flexibility	OP
Cost	Pearson Correlation	1	.618**	.476**	.394**	.203*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.021

	N	128	128	128	128	128
quality	Pearson Correlation	.618**	1	.589**	.659**	.429**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128
Time to deliver	Pearson Correlation	.476**	.589**	1	.651**	.462**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128
flexibility	Pearson Correlation	.394**	.659**	.651**	1	.585**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000
	N	128	128	128	128	128
OP	Pearson Correlation	.203*	.429**	.462**	.585**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.021	.000	.000	.000	
	N	128	128	128	128	128
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).						

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The above table shows the correlation matrix between logistics performance measures (i.e., cost, quality, time to deliver and flexibility) and organizational performance. The analysis of correlation matrix between each measures of logistics performance and organizational performance (OP) is given as below:

As shown in table 4.15 above, Pearson correlation test was conducted for cost and organizational performance (OP) the results indicates that there is positive and weak correlation between cost and organizational performance (OP) with correlation coefficient of 0.203 ($r=0.203$) and significance value is 0.021. On the other hand, as it is shown in the table 4.15 above there is moderate and positive relationship between quality measures of logistics performance and organizational performance with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.429 ($r=0.429$) and

significance value is 0.000. This significance tells that there is significant relationship between the two (quality measures of logistics performance and organizational performance). Also for time to deliver and organizational performance Pearson correlation test was conducted and the results shown in above table 4.15, there is moderate and positive significant correlation. In other words time to deliver and organizational performance have significant relationship with correlation coefficient of 0.462 ($r=0.462$) at significance value of 0.000. Furthermore correlation test between flexibility and organizational performance was also conducted as mentioned in table 4.15 above, the result shows that flexibility is positively related to organizational performance with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.585 ($r=0.585$) and significance value is 0.00. This significance tells that there is large effect and positive relationship between the two. Mansidao and Coelho (2014) also confirmed in their study findings supported positive relationships between logistics performance measures (cost, quality, time to deliver and flexibility) and organizational performance.

4.5.1.6 Correlation between collective logistics performance measures and organizational performance

Table 4.16-Correlation between collective logistics performance measures and organizational performance.

		logistics performance	organizational performance
logistics performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.456**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	128	128
organizational performance	Pearson Correlation	.456**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	128	128
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).			

Source: SPSS, 2018

According to Table 4.16 above it can be concluded that the logistics performance (collective logistics performance measures) and organizational performance has a moderate and positive relation based on Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.456 ($r=0.456$) with significance value of 0.01. This significance tells that there is genuine relationship between collective logistics

performance measures and organizational performance. In relation to this Ristovska et al., (2017) based on their finding described that success in logistics performance has a positive contribution for improvement of organizational performance.

4.5.2 Regression Analysis

So as to verify how the independent variable predicts the dependent variable, multiple linear regression analysis was conducted. Regression analysis is a statistical method to deal with the formulation of mathematical model depicting relationship among variables which can be used for the purpose of prediction of the value of dependent variable, given the value of the independent (Kothari, 2004). Therefore multiple linear regressions analysis was made to determine the predictive power of the independent variables (i.e. customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management, and warehouse management and logistics information system) on the dependent Variable (logistics performance) on the first regression. The second regression was also made to determine the predictive power of the independent variables (i.e. customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management, warehouse management and logistics information system) on the dependent Variable (organizational performance). The third regression was made to determine the predictive power of the independent variables logistics performance measures (i.e. logistics cost, logistics service quality, time to deliver and logistics flexibility) on the dependent Variable (organizational performance).

4.5.2.1 Multicollinearity Test

Absence of correlation between two or more independent variables (Multicollinearity) test is a prerequisite to proceed to regression analysis. In order to identify whether some of the independent variables have very high correlations with other independent variables, using collinearity diagnostics, multicollinearity estimate was performed. Saunders et al., (2007) suggested, if collinearity is discovered then one can either remove one of the variables or create a new variable that combine the previous two that were highly inter- correlated because when the predictor variables are highly correlated, they share essentially the same information and together, they may explain a great deal of the dependent variable, but may not individually contribute significantly to the model. Thus, the impact of multicollinearity is to reduce any individual independent variables predictive power by the extent to which it is associated with the other independent variables. Tolerance value is an indication of the percentage of variance in the

predictor that cannot be accounted for by the other predictors implying the fact that very small values indicate overlap or sharing of predictive power. Besides, if the VIF values of independent variables are beyond 10, then it is suggested that further investigation is required (Landau, and Everitt, 2004). Therefore, the multicollinearity test result of this particular study revealed that the tolerance values for all the independent variables are within the acceptable level of greater than 0.1, while the VIF values are also less than the maximum required value of 10. In this regard, it is possible to agree that multicollinearity is not a serious problem as long as this particular test result is concerned. The multicollinearity test result for each regression is available at **appendix-III**.

4.5.2.2 Normality Test

According to Hair et al. (2010), there are a variety of ways to check the normality of a data set i.e graphical (histogram and probability plot) and Hypothesis test for a test of normal (Shapiro-Wilk test and kolmogorov-smirnov test). Normal probability plot is a graphical method for assessing whether data come from a normal distribution. The plot compares the ordered data with what would be expected of perfectly normal data. A fairly linear pattern in a normal probability plot suggests that it is reasonable to assume that the data come from a normal distribution. If the data are normally distributed, then the dots on a normal probability plot will fall close to a straight line. For data that are not normal, the normal probability plot can help us determine how the data deviate from normality. The scatter should lie as close to the line as possible with no obvious pattern coming away from the line for the data to be considered normally distributed (Landau, and Everitt, 2004). The normality of the data set in this study is also tested using probability plot and it shows that the dots are follow along the straight line that is considered to be normal. The probability plot graphs for each regression is available at **appendix-IV**.

4.5.2.3 Heteroscedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test is part of the classical assumption test in regression model. To detect the presence or absence of heteroscedasticity in a data, can be done in several ways (i.e. Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg), one of them is by looking at the scatterplot graphs on SPSS outputs explained by Adams et al. (2007). The working principle of heteroscedasticity test with this method is to see the scatterplot graph between the predictive values of the independent variable that ZPRED with the residue of ZRESID. If there is a particular pattern in the spss scatterplot graphs, such as the points that form a regular pattern, it can be concluded that there has been a

problem of heteroscedasticity. Conversely, if there is no clear pattern and spreading dots, then the indication is no heteroscedasticity problem (Adams et al., 2007). Scatterplot graph have been used to test heteroscedasticity of the data. Based on the scatterplot test output using residuals versus predicted value, it appears that the spots are diffused and do not form a clear specific pattern. So it can be concluded that the regression model in this study does not occur heteroscedasticity problem. Heteroscedasticity test scatterplot graphs for each regression is available at **appendix-V**.

4.5.2.4 Regression of logistics performance on logistics practice dimensions

Table 4.17- Regression of logistics performance on logistics practice dimensions

Logistics Performance		R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
		.808 ^a	.653	.636	5.40781	
ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6663.036	6	1110.506	37.973	.000 ^b
	Residual	3538.568	121	29.244		
	Total	10201.603	127			
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
Coefficients	(Constant)	16.364	5.355		3.056	.003
	customer service	.658	.190	.257	3.456	.001
	inventory management	.110	.195	.038	.565	.573
	supply management	.318	.187	.120	1.701	.091
	transportation management	.088	.146	.042	.604	.547
	warehouse management	.137	.161	.068	.854	.395
	logistics information system	.991	.160	.461	6.209	.000

a. Dependent Variable: logistics performance

b. Predictors: (Constant), logistics information system, transportation management, inventory management, supply management, customer service, warehouse management.

Source: Field survey, 2018

As shown in the above table 4.17, the adjusted R Square is 0.636, this suggest that 63.6% of the variation in logistics performance is explained by the variables already incorporated in to the model. Therefore, in this particular case 0.636 adjusted R Square value revealed that 63.6% of the variation in the logistics performance is explained by the variables existed in the model. This further shows that only 36.4% of the variation in the dependent variable is to be determined by the variables outside of this model. The Multiple correlations R of +0.808 represent the combined correlation of all the independent variables and they are strongly correlated with the dependent variable.

As shown in the above table 4.17 the ANOVA test results demonstrated that the model is acceptable from statistical perspective. In other words, 0.000 levels of significances are obtained in all cases (i.e. customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management, warehouse management and logistics information system); this statistical condition further revealed that the regression models are statistically appropriate (fit) to the data set. Furthermore the *F* test result was 37.973 with significance of 0.000. This meant that the probability of these results occurring by chance was less than 0.05.

The large value of standardized beta coefficient in an independent variable has the more important determinant in predicting the dependent variable. The standardize beta coefficient value for logistics information system is 0.461. This implies that, this variable has relatively strong degree of importance for analyzing the effect of logistics dimensions on logistics performance than others. The standardized beta value for customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management and warehouse management are 0.257, 0.038, 0.120, 0.042 and 0.068 respectively. From the table 4.17 above the first regression model specified so far can be generated as: logistics performance= 0.257 customer service+ 0.038 inventory management + 0.12 supply management+ 0.042 transportation management + 0.068 warehouse management + 0.461 logistics information system.

The coefficient table depicts that the significant regression coefficients, such as customer service, and logistics information system are significant at probability value less than 0.05. This

significance level tells us that those variables uniquely contribute to the regression equation thereby making a significant contribution to the prediction. But, inventory management, supply management, transportation management and warehouse management are not significant in this data set since their probability is greater than 0.05. With respect to customer service and logistics information system this result is consistent with the finding by Bagshaw (2017) and Ristovska et al., (2017), who have got positive and significant relationship of logistics activities with logistics performance.

4.5.2.5 Regression of organizational performance on logistics practice dimensions

The table 4.18 below asserted that adjusted R Square of the model formulated regarding organizational performance is 0.259 that embraced the ability of the model in predicting the change in dependent variable by 25.9%. Moreover, the 0.259 adjusted R Square depicts that the model doesn't comprised 74.1% of the variables which can predict the dependent variable (organizational performance). The results also showed that a correlation value (R) of 0.542 which depicts that there is a good dependence between the independent and dependent variables.

Table 4.18-Regression of organizational performance on logistics practice dimensions

Organizational Performance		R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
		.542 ^a	.294	.259	2.76174	
ANOVA						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	384.295	6	64.049	8.397	.000 ^b
	Residual	922.893	121	7.627		
	Total	1307.188	127			
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		

Coefficients	(Constant)	11.088	2.735		4.054	.000
	customer service	.033	.097	.036	.341	.734
	inventory management	-.092	.100	-.089	-.922	.358
	supply management	-.075	.096	-.079	-.784	.434
	transportation management	.136	.075	.182	1.817	.072
	warehouse management	.041	.082	.057	.499	.619
	logistics information system	.361	.082	.469	4.430	.000
a. Dependent Variable: organizational performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), logistics information system, transportation management, inventory management, supply management, customer service, warehouse management.						

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The Table 4.18 above also shows the ANOVA results of the multiple regression analysis. The significance value of 0.000 indicates that the regression relationship is significant in predicting the effects of logistics practice dimensions on organizational performance of the firm. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table tests whether the overall regression model is a good fit for the data and the F ratio of 8.397 and the significance of 0.000 shows that there was not much difference in means between dependent and independent variables.

R-square value indicates only the variance in the organizational performance as it is explained by independent variables. When we look at the detail to what extent each independent variable influences the dependent variable: logistics information system was found to be determinant of organizational performance in this data set. The remaining statistically insignificant variables (i.e. customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management and warehouse management) are statistically insignificant to the dependent variable that is organizational performance since they have scored probability value out of the acceptable range ($p < 0.05$). In relation to the measuring power of the statistically significant variables the coefficient table revealed that logistics information system has a predicting standardized coefficient of 0.469 as per the table 4.18 above depicted. The second regression model specified in methodology section can be generated as: Organizational performance = 0.036 customer service - 0.089 inventory management - 0.079 supply management + 0.182 transportation management + 0.057 warehouse management + 0.469 logistics information system. Standardized regression

coefficient for logistics information system (=0.469), implies that a unit increase in logistics information system is likely to result in a 0.469 increase in organizational performance.

The only significant variable in the model is logistics information system since its significance value is less than 0.05. The other independent variables (customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management and warehouse management) are statistically insignificant in this data set since their respective significance value is greater than 0.05. With respect to logistics information system this result is similar with the finding by Mwangangi, (2016) and Gunasekaran and Ngai (2003) their study confirmed that logistics activities have positive contribution for organizational performance.

4.5.2.6 Regression of Organizational Performance on Logistics Performance Measures

As per the table 4.19 below there is causal relationship between logistics Performance measures and organizational performances. The value of adjusted R Square is 0.342, which implies that logistics performance measures (logistics cost, logistics service quality, time to deliver and flexibility) can account for 34.2% of the variation in organizational performance. Although there might be many factors that can explain the variable on organizational performance, approximately 34.2% of it is explained by logistics performance measures. This indicates that the remaining 65.8% of the variation in organizational performance cannot be explained by logistics Performance measures included in this model. The results also showed that a correlation value (R) of 0.602 which depicts that there is a good dependence between the independent and dependent variables.

Table 4.19-Regression of organizational performance on logistics performance measures

Organizational performance		R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
		.602 ^a	.362	.342	2.60320	
ANOVA result						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	473.662	4	118.415	17.474	.000 ^b
	Residual	833.526	123	6.777		

	Total	1307.188	127				
Model			Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
			B	Std. Error	Beta		
Coefficients	(Constant)	9.509	2.325			4.090	.000
	logistics cost	-.107	.085	-.118		-1.264	.209
	logistics service quality	.108	.112	.109		.967	.335
	time to deliver	.161	.104	.156		1.540	.126
	Logistics flexibility.	.395	.092	.458		4.286	.000
a. Dependent Variable: organizational performance							
b. Predictors: (Constant), logistics cost, logistics service quality, time to deliver, and logistics flexibility.							

Source: Field Survey, 2018

The ANOVA result table 4.19 above shows the overall significance/acceptability of the model from a statistical perspective. The F-ratio, which explain whether the result of the regression model could have occurred by chance or due to the contribution of the variables considered, has a value of 17.474 and is significant at 0.000. Large F value and a small significance level (typically smaller than 0.05 or 0.01) indicate that the results probably are not due to random chance. Therefore, it is possible to say that the regression model adopted in this study could have not occurred by chance and is considered significant.

Results of the regression coefficients presented in Table 4.19 above shows that the individual contribution of each predictor variable (logistics cost, logistics service quality, time to deliver and logistics flexibility) to the predicted variable (organizational performance) of the model. The standardized Beta coefficient value tells us about the relationship between organization performances with each predictor. The third regression model developed previously in the methodology part is generated as: $\text{organizational performance} = -0.118 \text{ logistics cost} + 0.109 \text{ logistics service quality} + 0.156 \text{ time to deliver} + 0.458 \text{ logistics flexibility}$. If other things remain constant a unit change in logistics flexibility would lead to a 0.458 change in organizational Performance.

From the coefficient table 4.19 above, only logistics flexibility is the most significant predictors which contributes 45.8% alone and significant value less than 0.05. The other predictor variables of the model logistics cost, logistics service quality and time to deliver are not significant in this data set since their significant value is greater than the required level that is 5%. The finding by Muslimin et al.,(2015) was indicated that logistics cost, logistics service quality have a positive significant impact on organizational performance but timeliness and logistics flexibility were insignificant in their finding. With respect to logistics flexibility this result is consistent with the finding by Ilic and Tesic, (2016) they found that logistics flexibility and other logistics performance measures (cost, quality and timeliness) have significant impact on organizational performance.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 INTRODUCTION

This Chapter presents the conclusion and recommendations resulting from the findings of the study. It is organized into four sections. The first section presents summary of the study findings in accordance with the objectives. The second section presents the conclusions from the study, the third section presents the recommendations resulting from the findings of the study and the last sections presents limitations of the study and further research directions, the subsections are presented below.

5.2 SUMMARY

As per the data analysis made in the previous chapter, major findings of the analysis are presented and summarized as below:-

- ❖ Regarding logistics practices of kombolcha textile Share Company majority of the respondents agreed that logistics customer service is practiced in the company. As per the finding indicated that the overall mean value of the items for customer service is (M=3.9102) which showed that the respondents agreed that customer service is practiced in the company. In spite of there is a sales and customer service function in principle; However, the qualitative results indicate that there are short comings in measuring and evaluating customer satisfaction level, stock outs due to capacity inefficiencies implying that still practiced less. Responses on inventory management also indicate that it is highly practiced in the company with overall mean value of items (M=3.8613) indicating that respondents agreed inventory management is practiced. But, the qualitative data result indicated that the company maintains too much inventory, inventory management tools like just in time and quick response have not been applied in the company all the time the company's logistics is flexible through maintaining inventories of raw and finished products and the associated costs are high and its inventory planning is based on guess from previous years yet have not applied economic order quantity and advance software inventory planning systems. Responses about supply management/procurement the overall mean value of items (M=3.9253) imply that respondents agreed that supply management is practiced in the company. Still the qualitative result signifies there are deficiencies on supply management the company have not been made formal supplier

performance evaluation and not providing incentives but the company makes agreements and contracts with suppliers that provide better prices, quality and delivery dates and has not been in a position to certification and reward programs for suppliers. The overall mean value for transportation management is (M=3.9619) indicating that respondents agreed that it is practiced denoted by the items in the company. But the qualitative data results the company's transportation service is not efficient, fail to minimize transit shipment, unable to truck on way freights due to the fact that the company does not applied advanced transport management tools. The overall mean value of Responses on warehouse management is (M= 4.1641) which depicted that respondents agreed that warehouse management is well practiced in the company. On the other hand qualitative data result showed that the company has not been applied lift trucks (loading and unloading is still manual), warehouse management system software's, radio frequency identification tool and advanced ICT tools to facilitate and maintain up to date record and reports of warehouse data. Regarding logistics information system the overall mean value of the responses is (3.7750) implying that respondents agreed that the company has integrated logistics information system to facilitate logistics functions. The qualitative result indicates that though it does not say logistics information system there is management information system function which facilitates information handling of the company. However; logistics information system components web based information system, application of advanced equipments for logistics activities, product identification and tracking systems such as bar code, EDI, RFID have not applied by the company that can facilitate logistics activities. Those logistics processes are also spread to procurement, property control, marketing and distribution and has no a single logistics department that is responsible to perform them all. In all this indicates that there is no well functioning logistics process in the company as the qualitative result signifies. Logistics function is responsible for most of asset management of any company so that not having best logistics practices facilitated by updated technologies is not the current principle in logistics since that will cost the company significant sales and customers. Concerning logistics performance of the company the overall mean value of responses on logistics cost is (M=3.8955) indicating that the respondents agreed that the company is capable of providing logistics activities at low cost. The overall mean value of responses on logistics

service quality/product is (M=4.2178) showing that the company's logistics service quality is high and providing products without quality problems. The overall mean value of time to deliver is (M=4.0313) implying that the company's logistics is capable of delivering orders timely. Responses on logistics flexibility the overall mean value is (M=3.9756) showing that the respondents agreed that the company's logistics system is responsive to changes. The qualitative data results indicated that the company's logistics related cost is sometimes high due to inventory costs and stock outs and the company's logistics is lag behind the schedule for foreign customers delivery requirements due to limited trucks, custom procedure problems and machine breakdowns. Responses on organizational performance indicated that 71.4% of the mean are greater than 3.41 showing that respondents agreed that there an increment in the company's financial and market related performance in the last five years with overall mean value (M=4.0491). The qualitative data revealed that there is significant improvement on quality of products and market acceptance stating that the company's products are short shelf life. The financial ratio of the company indicated that the return on investment of the company in 2012 was 0.0817 and it was 0.0178 in 2013, the total asset turnover ratio in 2012 was 1.4516 and it was 1.8728 in 2013.

- ❖ The correlation test result indicates that each logistics practice dimensions have significant and positive correlation with logistics performance that is customer service ($r=0.643$), inventory management ($r=0.485$), supply management ($r=0.579$), transportation management ($r=0.478$), warehouse management ($r=0.595$), and logistics information system ($r=0.737$). The Pearson correlation of combined logistics practice dimensions have positive and strong correlation($r=0.724$) with logistics performance at significance level less than 0.05. In other way, the regression model summary indicates logistics activities have also accounted 63.6% for the variability of logistics performance. On the other hand, the regression coefficient indicates that customer service and logistics information system have significant contribution for logistics performance with standardized beta coefficient 0.257 and 0.461 respectively with probability value less than 0.05. but, the other independent variables inventory management, supply management, transportation management and warehouse management are found to be

insignificant since their chance of occurrence is greater than 0.05 though they have positive standardized beta coefficient.

- ❖ The correlation test result indicates that each logistics practice dimensions have small up to medium through large effect and positive correlation with organizational performance that is customer service ($r=0.324$), inventory management ($r=0.224$), supply management ($r=0.279$), transportation management ($r=0.347$), warehouse management ($r=0.378$), and logistics information system ($r=0.511$). The Pearson correlation of combined logistics practice dimensions have positive and medium correlation ($r=0.417$) with organizational performance at significance value less than 0.05. In other way, the regression model summary indicates logistics practice dimensions have also accounted 25.9% for the variability of organizational performance. On the other hand, the regression coefficient indicates that logistics information system have significant contribution for organizational performance with standardized beta coefficient 0.469 with probability value less than 0.05. but, the other independent variables customer service, transportation management and warehouse management are insignificant since their chance of occurrence is greater than 0.05 though they have positive standardized beta coefficient and inventory management, supply management are insignificant and negative coefficients their probability of occurrence is above 0.05.
- ❖ The correlation test result of logistics performance measures and organizational performance indicated that each logistics performance measures have small to medium through large effect and significant positive correlation logistics cost ($r=0.203$), logistics service quality ($r=0.429$), time to deliver ($r=0.462$), and logistics flexibility ($r=0.585$), at significance level of 0.01 and 0.05. The Pearson correlation coefficient of collective logistics performance measures have medium and positive correlation ($r=0.456$) with organizational performance at significance level of 0.01. In addition, 34.2% of variability of organizational performance is explained by collective logistics performance measures. On the other hand the regression coefficient results indicate that only logistics flexibility has a significant standardized beta coefficient 0.458 and its chance of occurrence is less than 0.05. But the other logistics performance indicators cost, quality and time to deliver are insignificant due to their probability value is greater than 0.05.

5.3 CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study and the summary of findings the following conclusions are provided.

- Assessing the extent of logistics practices of kombolcha textile Share Company was one of the objectives that this study intends to achieve. Accordingly, the quantitatively obtained data suggested that logistics is well practiced in the company that majority of the respondents show their agreement about parameters of logistics dimensions customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management, warehouse management and logistics information system. However; qualitatively found data revealed that logistics is not as such understood to its best level so as to have a positive contribution to the company's performance by stating that customers complain for the absence of products when required, high inventory costs and long lead times, inefficiencies in capacity utilization due to machine breakdowns, inefficient transportation service, manual warehouse operations and have not been applied advance logistics tools that would enhance logistics system operations. Furthermore, with this study finding it is proved that logistics related costs of the company is high and the company's logistics is have not been capable of responding to the required time span and there is long cycle time in procurement.
- The other thing that can be inferred from this finding is that logistics dimensions (customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management, warehouse management and logistics information system) have significant and positive correlation with logistics performance and they are responsible for significant variation in logistics performance. Customer service and logistics information system have significant influence on logistics performance with probability value within the acceptable range. However; inventory management, supply management, transportation management and warehouse management have found to be statistically insignificant in this research data set since their respective chance of occurrence is greater than the acceptable value.
- In this study it is also found that logistics dimensions (customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management, warehouse management and logistics information system) have significant and positive correlation with

organizational performance and they are responsible for significant variation for organizational performance. Logistics information system is the only independent variable that have significant influence on organizational performance with probability value within the acceptable range. However; customer service, inventory management, supply management, transportation management and warehouse management have found to be statistically insignificant in this research data set since their respective chance of occurrence is greater than the acceptable value. This may be due to the fact that problems in the way of managing inventory, dealing with suppliers, inefficient transportation service, and due to hindrances in the warehouse operations.

- Furthermore, logistics performance (collective logistics performance measures) and organizational performance have significant and positive correlation that logistics performance measures account for a significant variation on organizational performance. Yet the only significant variable that significantly influences organizational performance in this study data set was logistics flexibility. The other logistics performance measures (logistics cost, quality and time to deliver) found to be insignificant in this research data set since the chance of occurrence of each is more than the required. this is perhaps due to the company's logistics related costs are high due to long lead times, frequent stock outs, the company's logistics system is not capable of responding time for customer orders. The finding of this study provides an addition to the existing literature with respect to customer service and logistics information system that have positive relationship and influence on logistics performance as well logistics information system has also proved a significant influence on organizational performance. In relation to this, the result is consistent with previous studies by (Mwangangi, 2016; Ilic and Tesic, 2016). But, in this research data set logistics practices dimensions inventory management, supply management, transportation management, warehouse management and logistics performance measures logistics cost, logistics service quality and time to deliver failed to have influence on organizational performance. This finding also has a great value for kombolcha textile share company's management and logistics personnel to understand their company's logistics functioning so as to revisit the process in managing logistics activities and to make changes to bring improvement in logistics activities so that logistics would result positive impact on overall profitability of the company.

5.4 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the study results and conclusions drawn above, some recommendations are proposed as a means of showing directions for overcoming the problems found.

- As evidenced from the qualitative data analysis the logistics activities are fragmented to various departmental units in the company customer service and distribution (transportation) in marketing; inventory control, supply, and warehouse in procurement and property control logistics information system in management information system. Therefore; the company should have a dedicated logistics department that would coordinate and facilitate all logistics functions together that optimize common objectives.
- Logistics practice dimension; logistics information system have significant positive contribution for organizations performance. Therefore; The company should be better to work more on logistics information system and should employ technologies such as electronic data interchange, e-procurement, barcode systems, radio frequency data communication, web based logistics and radio frequency identification to coordinate its logistics functions.
- The other logistics practice dimensions inventory management, supply management, transportation management and warehouse management have positive correlation with organizational performance but found to be insignificant on the regression. So that the company is recommended to bring significant changes on the management of such insignificant logistics activities. The company should develop and adept customer service policy, electronic order processing and order status visibility, monitoring customer satisfaction on consistent basis, and adopt just in time principles, quick response, real time inventory visibility with customers and suppliers, information sharing on inventory status, full capacity utilization and would apply advanced inventory planning tools like economic order quantity, material resource planning and integrated enterprise resource planning to improve its customer service and inventory management. KTSC should develop suppliers service policy maintain regular performance evaluation, electronic information sharing and should employ transport management system to ensure effective and efficient distribution systems, tracking system such as GPS to know where vehicles are available and regular performance evaluation. The company should also made improvements on its way of warehouse operations by applying warehouse management

systems, maximize warehouse space utilization to make sure that materials and products are protected and their value is maximized. By doing so those insignificant logistics dimensions can bring the potential positive contribution to the company. Furthermore, in such way the company can enhance system wide logistics functions, work together with customers and suppliers, transport goods quickly and safely, economical use of logistics resources thereby the company can enhance product value, cost reduction, maximize revenue and market value of the company.

- This finding also shows that logistics performance has positive correlation with organizational performance but the regression coefficient proved that only logistics flexibility is significant with probability value below 0.05; the other logistics performance measures logistics cost, logistics service quality/product, and time to deliver found to be insignificant. Therefore; the company should focus on logistics cost reduction on inventory and safety stocks, efficient in capacity utilization, minimize distribution costs and investment on innovations that could improve the quality of the company's logistics system and products like continual improvement programs, formal quality assurance system and statistical process controls to increase total logistics quality. The company should also meet customers' delivery due dates, timely delivery, promised delivery windows and tracking of order movements. In such away the company can accomplish the full benefits of logistics as mentioned in the literature section and those insignificant variables can have a positive influence for the company's performance.

Just I have seen all of things mentioned on this questionnaire on my daily work but I don't think that they are applied in such detailed degree. This was the idea putted on the comment section of the questionnaire by one of the respondents. Having logistics function in a company may be a good stance to go through superior logistics performance but all elements of logistics activities needs to be incorporated and assisted with advanced logistics equipments to have a positive influence on revenue generation of a company. As stated by Frazelle, (2002), Real breakthroughs in logistics are achieved when new ways are found to substitute information for inventory and work content. Therefore; kommbolcha textile share company has to visit, update its way of managing logistics activities apply IT solutions on its logistics process so that logistics activities would bring a positive contribution on the overall performance of the company.

5.5 LIMITATION AND FURTHER RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This study is conducted at only one company (kombolcha textile Share Company) so that it may possible to extend the result to other textile factory and the instruments were distributed purposively. The research considers internal logistics process of the company and has not included the company's partner's customers, suppliers and transport carriers. The company was also not willing to provide recent financial and market related reports due to confidentiality nature. Therefore; future studies should consider expanding their scope to include the whole textile companies in Ethiopia and expanding the evaluation to customers, suppliers and transport carriers or futures studies would look the evaluation of the companies' logistics from the customers and suppliers perspective. Furthermore future studies can also extend research on logistics practice to other manufacturing industries like food and brewery, wood and metal products, service sectors with varying research instruments and the result may be changed in those conditions.

REFERENCE

- Adams, J., Khan, H.T.A., Raeside, R. and White, D. (2007). *Research Methods for Graduate Business and Social Science Students* (1sted.). Vivek Mehra for Response Books, New Delhi, India.
- Addishiwot N. (2016). *Assessment of Logistics Performance in Flower Industry: The Case of Floriculture Company* (master thesis). Addis Ababa University, School of commerce, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Afomeya, T. (2016). *The effects of logistics management practice on the performance of food manufacturing industry* (master thesis). Addis Ababa University, school ocommerce, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Alberto, P. (2000). The Logistics of Industrial Location Decisions: An Application of the Analytic Hierarchy Process Methodology. *International Journal of Logistics*, 3(3), pp. 273-289.
- Ali, M.R., Jaafar, S. H., and Mohamad, S. (2008). Logistics and Supply Chain in Malaysia: Issues and Challenges. EASTS International Symposium on Sustainable Transportation: Incorporating Malaysian Universities Transport Research Forum Conference (pp.1-11). Universiti Teknologi Malaysia, Malaysia.
- Aydın, U. (2014). Envisioning E-logistics Developments in Turkey on the Way of Accession to the EU: A Focus Group Study. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(7), pp. 505-525.
- Bagshaw, K. B. (2017). Integrating Logistics Management through Warehousing and Inventory Management to Spawn High Market Share and Profitability. *Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research*, 39(2017), pp. 58-68.
- Bae, H., S. (2016). The Moderating Effect of Logistics Information Systems on Inter-organizational Collaboration and Performance of Korean Shipping and Logistics Firms. *International Journal of e -Navigation and Maritime Economy*, 5 (2016), pp. 085 – 096
- Ballou, H.R. (2007). *The Evolution and Future of Logistics and Supply Chain Management: European Business Review*. Case Western Reserve University; Weather head School of Management, Cleveland Ohio, USA.
- Biggam, J. (2008). *Succeeding with your Master's Dissertatio: A step-by-step handbook*. McGraw Hill, London, UK.

- Biniyam, G. (2016). *The effect of supply chain integration on operational performance in Ethiopian trading enterprises* (master thesis). Addis Ababa University, school of commerce, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Bowersox, D. J., Closs, D. J., and Cooper, M. B. (2002). *Supply Chain Logistics Management* (1sted.). McGraw-Hill, NY, USA.
- Brewer, M.A. (Eds.) (2001). *Integrated logistics strategies: Handbook of Logistics and Supply Chain Management*. Elsevier Science Ltd, Heriot-Watt University, Edinburgh, Germany.
- Bureau of Transport Economics (2001). *Logistics in Australia: A Preliminary Analysis*. Canberra, Australia: author.
- Burman, R. (1995). *Manufacturing Management: Principles and Systems*. McGraw-Hill Book Company, London, England.
- Campagna, A. (2009). Logistics Performance Metrics.
- Celebi, D., Bayraktar, D., and Bingol, L. (2010). Analytical Network Process for logistics management: A case study in a small electronic appliances manufacturer. *Computers and Industrial Engineering*, 58 (2010), pp. 432–441.
- Chow, G., Heaver, T.D. and Henriksson, L.E. (1994). Logistics Performance: Definition and Measurement, *International Journal of Physical Distribution and Logistics Management* 24 (7), pp. 17-28.
- Christopher, M. (2011). *Logistics and Supply Chain Management* (4th ed.). Prentice Hall, London, UK,
- Closs, D., and Thompson, C. (1999). Logistics physical resource management. *Journal of Business Logistics*, 13(2), pp. 269-283.
- Creswell, J.W. (2012). *Educational research: Planning, conducting and evaluating quantitative and qualitative research* (4th ed.). Pearson Education Inc, NY, USA.
- Creswell, J. W. (2009). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative and mid approaches* (3rd ed.). Sage Publication, London, UK.
- Daniel, K. and Amare, M. (n.d.). Competitiveness for Ethiopian textile and garment industries: *A way forward*. 2nd National Workshop on “Future Prospects and the Role of Textile and Garment Sectors in Achieving the Millennium Development Goals of Ethiopia” (pp. 1-17). Addis Ababa, Ethiopia.
- Dawson, C. (2002). *Practical Research Methods: A user-friendly guide to mastering research*

- techniques and projects* (1st ed.). How To Books Ltd, Newtec place, United Kingdom.
- Demeter, K. (2003). Manufacturing strategy and competitiveness. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 81(82), pp. 205–213.
- Dubey, R. (2008). Improving firm performance through logistics activities: a research framework. *Indian Journal of Commerce and Management Studies*, 3(7), pp. 2229-5674
- Fekadu M. Debela (2013). *Logistics Practices in Ethiopia* (Independent thesis 2013:09). Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Department of Energy and technology.
- Frazzle, E. (2002). *Supply Chain Strategy: the logistics of supply chain management* (1st ed.). McGraw-Hill Companies, NY, USA.
- Gacuru, W. (2015). Factors affecting efficiency in logistics performance of trading and distribution firms based in jomo kenyatta international airport area. *International Academic Journal of Procurement and Supply Chain Management*, 1(5), pp. 50-71.
- Green Jr. K.W., Whitten D., and Inman R. A. (2008). The impact of logistics performance on organizational performance in a supply chain context. *An International Journal*, 13(4), pp. 317–327
- George and Mallery (2003). *Business Research Methods*. Oxford University Press, London, UK.
- Gunasekaran A, Ngai, E. W. T. and Cheng, T. C. E. (2007). Developing an E-logistics System: A Case Study. *International Journal of Logistics Research and Applications*, 10(4), pp. 333-349.
- Gunasekaran, A. and Ngai, E.W.T. (2003). The successful management of a small logistics company. *International Journal of Physical Distribution and Logistics Management*, 33(9), pp. 25-42.
- Hair, JR. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., and Anderson, R.E. (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis* (7th ed.). *Pearson prentice hall*.
- Harrison, A., and Hoek, R. V. (2008). *Logistics Management and Strategy: Competing through the supply chain* (3rd Ed.). Pearson Education Limited, Edinburgh Gate, England.
- Ilic, D., and Tesic A. (2016). The relationship between supply chain management strategy, marketing, logistics and company performance for breweries in serbia. *Economics of Agriculture, EP 2016*, 4(63), pp. 1157-1168.
- International trade center (2016) *Textile and Clothing value chain roadmap of Ethiopia 2016 2020*. Geneva, Switzerland: Author.

- Kaple, V., and Jadha, T. (2017). *Textile unit logistics* Retrieved from <http://www.fibre2fashion.com/industry-article/5837/the-logistics-management-in-textile-industry>
- Karagoz, B., and Akgun, E.A. (2015). The roles of IT capability and organizational culture on logistics capability and firm performance. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, 7(2), pp.26-38.
- Keebler, J.S. and Plank, R.E. (2009). Logistics performance measurement in the supply chain: a benchmark. *Benchmarking: An International Journal* 16 (6), pp. 785-798
- Ketikidis K. H, Koh S. C. L., Dimitriadis N., Gunasekaran, A., and Kehajova, M. (2008). The Use of Information Systems for Logistics and Supply Chain Management in South East Europe: Current Status and Future Directions. *Omega-International Journal of Management Science*, 36(4), pp. 592-599.
- Kirui, M. T. and Nondi, R. (2017). Effects of logistics management on the organization performance of shipping firms in mombasa county. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 3 (9), pp 1194-1200.
- Koin V. R, Cheruiyot G. K., and Mwangangi, P. (2014). Effect of Inventory Management on the Supply Chain Effectiveness in the Manufacturing Industry in Kenya: A Case Study Of Tata Chemicals Magadi. *International Journal of Social Sciences Management and Entrepreneurship* 1(2), pp. 189-202.
- Kothari, C.R. (2004). *Research methodology: methods and techniques* (2nd Ed.). New age international publisher, New Delhi, India.
- Kotsifaki, M., Dimitriadis, N., Ketikidis, H. P. and Missopoulos, F. (2007). Logistics strategic planning: current status and future prospects in Greek companies. *International journal of Risk assessment and management*, 7 (1), Pp. 44-58.
- Kumar, A., Ozdamar, L., and Zhang, C. N. (2008). Supply Chain Redesign in the Healthcare Industry of Singapore. *Supply Chain Management: An International Journal*, 13(2), pp. 95-103.
- Laird, M. (2012). *Logistics Management: A Firm's Efficiency Performance Model* (BBA Thesis). Presented to Ohio state University, USA.
- Landau, S. and Everitt, S. B. (2004). *A Handbook of Statistical Analysis using SPSS* (1st Ed.) Chapman and Hall/CRC Press LLC, FL, USA.

- Lawrence, D., Fredendall, and Ed, H. (2001). *Basics of supply chain management* (1st ed.). St. Lucie Press/APICS series on resource management, FL, USA.
- Leedy P.D. and Ormrod J. E. (2010). *Practical research: planning and design* (9th edition). Pearson Education, NJ, USA.
- Lummus, R.R., Krumwiede, D.W. and Vokurka, R.J. (2001).The Relationship of Logistics to Supply Chain Management: Developing a Common Industry Definition. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 101(8), pp. 426–432.
- Mansidao Rui M., andCoelhoLuis A.G. (2014). Logistics Performance: a theoretical conceptual model for small and medium enterprises. School of Technology of Setuba and Management Department, Evora Universityworking paper.
- Melkamu, A. (2016). *Logistics practices in Ethiopian medium and large leather footwear manufacturing firms* (master thesis). Addis ababa university, school of commerce, Addis Ababa,Ethiopia.
- Meng, Y. (2006).The effect of Inventory on the Supply Chain (diploma work).Vaxijo University, School of Technology and Design.
- Melovic, B., Mitrovic, S., Djokaj, A., andVatin, N. (2015). Logistics in the Function of Customer Service: Relevance for the Engineering Management. International Scientific Conference Urban Civil Engineering and Municipal Facilities,Procedia Engineering 117 (2015), pp. 802 – 807.
- Mentzer, J.T., Flint, D.J. and Hult, G.T.M. (2001).Logistics service quality as a segment customized process. *Journal of Marketing* 65 (40), pp. 82-104.
- Mitra, S., andDatta, P. P. (2013). A survey of sustainable supply chain management practices in Indian manufacturing firms (working paper series). Indian institute of management, Calcutta, India.
- Moore,Y.N., Baldwin H.L., Camm, F., and Cook, R. C.(2002).Implementing Best Purchasing and Supply Management Practices: Lessons from Innovative Commercial Firms. Prepared for the United States Air Force, RAND, Santa Monica.
- Mukolwe, A. G. and Wanyoike.M.D. (2015).An assessment of the effect of logistics management practices on operational efficiency at mumias sugar companylimited Kenya. *International journal of economics, commerce and management*,3(6), pp. 1134 1156.

- Murphy, J., Paul, R., and Wood, F. (2008). *Contemporary Logistics* (9th Ed.). Prentice Hall, New Delhi, India.
- Muslimin, Hadi, S. and Ardiansyah (2015). The relationship between logistics and financial performance of SMEs in Indonesia. *I J A B E R*, 13 (7): pp. 4805-4814.
- Mwangangi, P.W. (2016). *Influence of logistics management on performance of manufacturing firms in Kenya* (PhD dissertation). Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Nairobi, Kenya
- Neely, A., Gregory, M. and Platts, K. (2005). Performance measurement system design: A literature review and research agenda. *International Journal of Operations and Production Management*, 25 (12) pp. 1228-1263.
- Neuman, W.L. (2014). *Social research methods: quantitative and qualitative approaches* (7th ed.). Pearson Education Inc, London, UK.
- Njambi, E. and Katuse, P. (2013). Third party logistics in distribution efficiency delivery for competitive advantage in fast moving consumer goods companies in Kenya. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Entrepreneurship* 1 (8), pp. 15-27.
- Odhiambo, H., Onyango, R., Kibet, Y., and Kimutahi, G. (2017). Effect of Logistics Activities on Performance of Agro Processing Firms in Uasin Gishu County, Kenya. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 19(12), PP. 21-28.
- Ogbad, E. E. (2009). Profitability through Effective Management of Materials. *Journal of Economics and International Finance*, 1(4), pp. 099-105
- Ondoro, O.C., Ojera, B.P., and Oginda, N. M. (2013). Role of strategic purchasing and supply management practices in firm performance: A lesson from public bus transport firms in Kenya. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Social Science*, 2(8), pp. 187-201.
- Ozalp, I., Suvaci, B., and Tonus, H.Z. (2010). A new approach in logistics management: just in time-logistics (JIT-L). *International journal of business and management studies*, 2(1), pp. 37-45.
- Pallant, J. (2007). *SPSS survival manual: a step-by-step guide to data analysis using SPSS for windows* (3rd Ed.). open university publisher, NY, USA.
- Qadir, I., and Ali, A. (2017). Importance of Logistics Processes for Customer Service and Firm Performance: Evidence from Furniture Industry of Pakistan. *Journal of Sustainable Business and Management Solutions in Emerging Economies*, 22(3), pp. 27-36.

- Ran, T. (2009). *Internal Logistics as a Part of Supply Chain* (master thesis). Lahti University Of Applied Sciences, Faculty of Business Studies, Nokia-China, Dongguang Branch.
- Reichheld, F. (1996). The customers you lose hold the information you need to succeed. *Customer Defections: Harvard business school*.
- Richard, J.P., Devinney, M. T., Yip, S. G., and Johnson, G. (2009). Measuring Organizational Performance: Towards Methodological Best Practice. *Journal of Management*, 35(3), pp. 718-804.
- Ristovska, N., Kozuharov, S., and Petkovski, V. (2017). The Impact of Logistics Management Practices on Company's Performance. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Sciences*, 7(1), pp. 245–252.
- Robinson, A. (2013). *What is Transportation and Logistics Management* (Eds). Retrieved from <http://cerasis.com/2013/08/13/transportation-and-logistics-management/>.
- Rodrigue, J.P. (2012). *Supply Chain Management: Logistics Changes and the Concept of Friction*. P.V. Hall and M. Hesse, London, UK.
- Sandberg, E., Kihlen, T. and Abrahamsson, M. (2011). Characteristics of a Logistics-Based Business Model. *Journal of Marketing Channels*, (18), pp. 1-23.
- Sarkis, J., and Sundarraj, R. (2002). Hub location at Digital Equipment Corporation: a comprehensive analysis of qualitative and quantitative factors. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 137(2), pp.33-47.
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., and Thornhill, A. (2007). *Research Methods for Business Students* (4th ed.). Pearson Education Limited, Edinburgh Gate, England.
- Savitskie, K.P. (2003). *The impact of logistics strategy and logistics information technology process on service performance* (PhD dissertation). Michigan state university, NJ, USA.
- Sekaran, U. (2003). *Research method for business: A skill building approach* (4th ed.), John Wiley and Sons publisher, NY, USA.
- Shang, K.C., and Marlow, P. B. (2007). The effects of logistics competency on performance. *Journal of International Logistics and Trade*, 5 (2), pp.45-66.
- Somekh, B., and Lewin, C. (Eds.) (2005). *Research methods in the social sciences* (1st ed.). SAGE Publications, London, England.
- Somuyiwa, A.O., and Adewoye, J.O. (2010). Managing Logistics Information System: Theoretical Underpinning. *Asian Journal of Business Management* 2(2), pp. 41-47.

- Stock, G. N., Greis, N. P., and Kasarda, J. D. (2000). Enterprise logistics and supply chain structure: the role of fit. *Journal of Operations Management*, 18(2000), pp. 531–547.
- Stock, J. R., and Lambert, D. M. (2001). *Strategic Logistics management* (4th ed.). McGraw-Hill, Singapore, country.
- Suhong, L., Ragu-Nathanb, B., Ragu-Nathanb, T.S., and Subba Raob, S. (2006). The impact of supply chain management practices on competitive advantage and organizational performance. *The international journal of management science Omega*, 34 (2006), pp. 107 – 124.
- Swerdlik, C. (2009). *Psychological Testing and Assessment: Anntroduction to Tests and Measurement* (7thed.). McGraw Hill Primis, NY, USA.
- Tseng, Y. and Yue, W. L. (2005). The role of transportation in logistics chain. *Proceedings of the Eastern Asia Society for Transportation Studies*, 5(2005), pp. 1657 – 1672.
- Tura, K.H. and Efa G.T. (2017). The Role of Logistic in Agribusiness Firm in Ethiopia. *IndustrialEngineering Letters*, 7(5), pp. 07-13
- Virolainen, V.M. (1991). Control Systems for LogisticsPerformance: International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis, A-2361, Laxenburg, Austria.
- Wang, X. (2013). *The determinants of textile and apparel export performance in Asian countries* (Graduate Thesis and Dissertations). Iowa State University Digital Repository, 13642.
- Waters, D. (2003) *Logistics: An Introduction to Supply Chain Management* (1st Ed.). palgrave macmillan, New York, USA.
- Waters, D. (Eds.). (2010). *Global logistics: new directions in supply chain management* (6th ed.). Kogan Page Limited, London, United Kingdom.

APPENDIX I- Questionnaire

AKSUM UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS
DEPARTMENT OF LOGISTICS AND SUPPLY CHAIN MANAGEMENT
POSTGRADUATE PROGRAM

QUESTIONNAIRE

The main aim of this questionnaire is to collect primary data for conducting a research on the topic **‘The Effect of logistics practice on organizational performance’ in your company for partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of the degree of Master of arts in logistics and supply chain management.** In this regard, I kindly request you to provide me reliable information for each item after you have read carefully. Please complete each part of the questionnaire with utmost care, with commitment, and honesty. The answer you provide will kept with Confidential and will not be used for other purpose except for intended research purpose. I would like to extend deep-heart thanks for your polite cooperativeness and appreciate more for the answer that you give are secretly kept.

General instruction:

- There is no need of writing your name
- For part I put (x) in the appropriate row where answer options are available and write your age, years stayed in the organization and department name.
- For part II circle the appropriate number for each statement

In case you have any question and confusion in completing this questionnaire contact me at:

Phone No.: 0913618003

E-mail: amanuelmengistu145@gmail.com

Thank you in advance for your Kind Cooperation !!!!!

Part I: personal information

Sex	Male (1)
	Female (2)
Age	
Level of education	College diploma
	First degree
	Second degree and above
Years stayed in the organization	
Your department/work unit:	

Part II: Questionnaire for logistics practices, logistics performance and organizational performance

Section one: Logistics practices

With regard to logistics practices of your organization, please circle the appropriate number to indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with each statement. The item scales are five-point Likert type scales with 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree.

Customer service management (CS):						
1.	We have clearly defined customer service policy.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	We frequently monitor our Customers level of satisfaction.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	We have customer friendly order capture and entry.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	We have various options for our customers to place and enter their orders. (e.g, telephone, mail, fax, internet).	1	2	3	4	5
5.	We have maintained real time inventory visibility to our customers.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	We have able to maintain flexible customer Order processing proactive to changes.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	We communicate quickly with customers if unusual changes occur.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	We have multiple collection and payment options. (e.g, mobile banking, electronic transfer, internet banking)	1	2	3	4	5
	Inventory planning and management (IM):					

1.	We have established inventory planning and control policy.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	With Improved forecast accuracy we have able to minimize lost sales and customer dissatisfactions.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	We have able to reduced lead times with efficient inventory planning. (e.g., economic order quantity).	1	2	3	4	5
4.	We frequently achieve lower purchase order/setup costs.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	We able to maintain minimum inventory with quick response and just in time.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	We frequently carious to make the various inventory carrying costs to the minimum.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	We able to maintain improved inventory visibility with our suppliers.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	We frequently deployed optimal inventory to customer's location timely.	1	2	3	4	5
	Supply management (SM):					
1.	We have clearly established supplier service policy.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	We monitor and evaluate our suppliers' performance on a consistent basis.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	We have clearly defined criteria to select our suppliers.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	We have established criterion for supplier certification and reward.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	We maintained proactive exception reporting with suppliers.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	We frequently exchange information via electronic communication with suppliers (e.g. EDI, fax, and e-procurement).	1	2	3	4	5
7.	We have able to improve supply quality via supply base rationalization.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	We able to reduce acquisition costs through purchase consolidation.	1	2	5	4	5
9.	We have practicing electronic fund transfer when payment to suppliers.	1	2	3	4	5
10.	We have maintained strong partnership and collaboration with suppliers.	1	2	3	4	5
	Transportation management (TM):					
1.	We have efficient transportation services in moving materials.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	We able to achieve in transit Shipments to the minimum.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	We have visible shipment status information.	1	2	3	4	5

4.	We have collaborative relationship with our transport Carriers.	1	1	3	4	5
5.	We have clear freight management principles.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	We have flexible Transportation service that can handle changes.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	We have achieved economies of scale via transport consolidation.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	We frequently Measure transport performance for delivery of our finished products.	1	2	3	4	5
9.	We frequently Measure the transport performance of transport companies and rewarding them accordingly.	1	2	3	4	5
	Warehouse management (WM):					
1	We able to design a warehouse convenient for loading and unloading.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	We have standard guidelines to receive and store materials.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	We always properly store materials and timely disbursing to user functions.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	We receive materials with assurance of quantity and quality as per ordered.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	We have able to minimize damages of product in the warehouse.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	We have maintained up to date records and reports of warehouse data.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	We have adequate shelves in warehouse to facilitate order picking.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	We able to packaged and boxed products for more convenient for use.	1	2	3	4	5
9.	We have skilled personnel that can handle warehouse activities.	1	2	3	4	5
	Logistics information system(LIS):					
1.	We have faster and Smooth information flow to all logistics functions.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	We able to provide web-based information system for all clients.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	We have provided basic communication tools such as email, telephone, fax, etc for logistics activities.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	We have used product identification and tracking system (such as bar code, EDI, IT solution or RFID) to support logistics activities.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	We maintain easier collection/payable management with logistics information system.	1	2	3	4	5

6.	We frequently are looking for new or technologically-advanced equipments for logistics operations.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	We have achieved optimal inventory with accurate information.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	We able to minimize operational costs with logistics information system.	1	2	3	4	5
9.	We have able to achieve smooth flow of materials and products.	1	2	3	4	5
10.	We have Used electronic customer feedback.	1	2	3	4	5

Section two: logistics performance (LP)

With regard to logistics performance of your company, please circle the appropriate number to indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with each statement. The item scales are five-point Likert type scales with 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = neutral, 4 = agree, 5 = strongly agree.

	Logistics cost (LC): an organization is capable of carrying out logistics activities at low cost.					
1.	We able to meet customer requirements at low cost.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	We able to achieve efficient capacity utilization.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	We able to minimize cost with safety stocks.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	We able to minimize cost with continuous improvement philosophy.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	We run operation with less Production cost.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	We maintains low manpower costs as compared to main competitors	1	2	3	4	5
7.	We achieve low distribution costs as compared to main competitors.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	We able to provide competitive prices.	1	2	3	4	5
	Quality (LQ): our company is capable of offering product quality and Performance that creates higher value for our customers.					
1.	We offer high quality products to our customer.	1	2	3	4	5

2.	We billed invoices accurately.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	We deliver product orders without damage.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	We maintain stock out level to the minimum.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	We fulfilled orders accurately.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	We deliver orders with greater shipping accuracy.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	We achieve high Percentage of orders without quality problems.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	We Employ continual improvement programs for sustainable quality.	1	2	3	4	5
	Time to Delivery (TD): an organization is capable of providing on time the type and volume of product required by customers.					
1.	We deliver customer order on time.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	We frequently minimize delivery lead time.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	We frequently able to minimize purchase Order cycle-time.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	We Offer greater percentage of accurate timely delivery.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	We enter customer orders timely.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	We provide dependable delivery.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	We solve customer complaints in short time.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	We achieve short order processing time.	1	2	3	4	5
	Flexibility (LF): an organizations Responsiveness to customer requirements.					
1.	We have responsive logistic system to special orders.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	We have responsive logistic system to the instability of environment.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	We are flexible to acceptable number of changes by orders.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	We Accommodate delivery time for specific needs of customers.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	We have Quicker responses to changes with suppliers.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	We able to cope with the range of customer demand.	1	2	3	4	5

7.	We offer frequent deliveries for customers.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	We able to meet precise needs of customers in less time.	1	2	3	4	5

Section three: organizational performance (OP)

Regarding organizational performance of your company, please circle appropriate number which best indicate your firm's overall performance. The item scales are five-point Likert scales with 1 = significant decrease, 2 = decrease, 3=same as before, 4=increase, 5=significant increase.

	Organizational performance (OP): how well your company achieves its market-oriented goals as well as its financial goals in the past five years?					
1.	Market share.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	The growth of market share.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	The growth of sales.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	Return on investment.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	Growth in return on investment.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	Profit margin on sales.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	Overall competitive position.	1	2	3	4	5

If you have any comment, you well come:

APPENDIX II- Interview Questions

Semi –structured Interview questions

1. What is your view about your company's logistics practice?
2. How do you describe your company's relationship with its customers?
3. How your company does manage and controls its inventory? What type of inventory management tools your company utilizes to minimize inventory related costs (ordering, insurance, holding and stock outs)?
4. How do you describe your company's relationship with suppliers? What benefits your company has ever achieved as a result of having collaborative relationship with suppliers?
5. Do you believe your company's transport function is capable to provide material inputs to production and to deliver finished products to customers?
6. Does your company have a warehouse facility convenient for storage of material inputs and products and easy accessible to deployment?
7. Does your company have logistics information system that facilitates logistics functions? What benefits or advantages your company have ever gained with having logistics information system?
8. How your company does measures the performance of logistics function?
9. What contribution does logistics performance has to the well functioning of your company?
10. How do you measure your company's overall performance? Have you seen any improvement of your company in the last five years?

Appendix III-Multicollinearity Test

Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics		
	Tolerance	VIF	
1	customer service	.520	1.924
	inventory management	.625	1.600
	supply management	.580	1.724
	transportation management	.580	1.723
	warehouse management	.454	2.202
	logistics information system	.521	1.920

a. Dependent Variable: logistics performance

Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics		
	Tolerance	VIF	
1	customer service	.520	1.924
	inventory management	.625	1.600
	supply management	.580	1.724
	transportation management	.580	1.723
	warehouse management	.454	2.202
	logistics information system	.521	1.920

a. Dependent Variable: organizational performance

Coefficients^a

Model	Collinearity Statistics		
	Tolerance	VIF	
1	cost	.592	1.689
	quality	.406	2.465
	time to deliver	.508	1.968
	flexibility	.454	2.202

a. Dependent Variable: organizational performance

Appendix IV-Normality Test

Appendix V- Heteroscedasticity Test

